

Energy

Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	EGY-D-21-06511R2
Article Type:	Full length article
Keywords:	Hybrid cooling; Pilot Plant; Water Consumption Saving; Experimental Characterization; Optimal operating strategies
Corresponding Author:	Patricia Palenzuela, PhD Palaforma Solar de Almería-CIEMAT Almería, Province SPAIN
First Author:	Patricia Palenzuela, PhD
Order of Authors:	Patricia Palenzuela, PhD Lidia Roca Faisal Asfand Kumar Patchigolla
Abstract:	<p>The new challenge of the European Commission is to limit water consumption in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants, especially significant in the cooling process. Hybrid cooling systems are presented as a potential solution to achieve water consumption reduction since they also avoid a high penalty of efficiency loss in the power block. In this work, a hybrid cooling pilot plant installed at Plataforma Solar de Almería is evaluated experimentally. The system has been tested under different ambient and operating conditions to analyze their influence on the water and electricity consumption. The results reveal that significant water savings were achieved in comparison with the conventional only-wet configuration. Concretely, a maximum water consumption saving of 67% was found at high ambient temperatures (between 25 and 30 °C) and for a thermal load of 80% when a hybrid configuration was used. The optimal operating strategies that achieve a tradeoff between low water and electricity consumption have been identified by two efficiency indexes: the specific electricity and water consumption. The parallel configuration was the optimal one in most of the cases. At high ambient temperatures and 80% thermal load, the electricity and water consumptions of this configuration were 0.033 kWe/kWth and 0.071 L/kWth, respectively.</p>

Highlights

- Test campaign to investigate the optimal configurations of a hybrid cooler
- Trade-off between water and electric energy consumption under several conditions
- Specific electricity consumption and specific water consumption for the evaluation
- Maximum water consumption saving of 67% for parallel configuration split ratio 25%
- Maximum electricity reduction of 59% for parallel configuration split ratio 50%

Almería 16 December 2021

Editor
Energy

Dear Editor,

Attached you can find the article whose name is “Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants” wrote by Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Lidia Roca, Dr. Faisal Asfand and Dr. Kumar Patchigolla.

This work presents the results of an exhaustive experimental campaign aiming the assessment of the best operating strategies of a hybrid cooling system in terms of reduction in the water and electricity consumptions in comparison with the conventional only-dry and only-wet cooling systems. The test campaign has been carried out at a hybrid cooling pilot plant installed at the Plataforma Solar de Almería under the frame of an European project, which allows the testing of different configurations under a wide range of operating (different thermal loads) and ambient (different ambient temperatures) conditions. This flexibility allows simulating the integration of the hybrid cooling system into the power block of a CSP plant. Therefore, the results obtained from this study can be of special interest for CSP research and industry whose new challenge is to limit the water consumption in CSP plants (especially in the cooling system) due to the significant water scarcity in those locations where they are installed.

Please, consider the paper for its publication in Energy.

Yours, sincerely

Patricia Palenzuela

Project Researcher
Solar Thermal Applications Unit
Plataforma Solar de Almería
Carretera de Senés km. 4; P.O.BOX 22
04200 Tabernas (Almería), Spain
Phone: (+34) 950 387800 Ext. 909 Fax: (+34) 950 365015
Email: patricia.palenzuela@psa.es
URL: www.psa.es

Credit author statement

Patricia Palenzuela: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft **Lidia Roca:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft **Faisal Asfand:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing **Kumar Patchigolla:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

DATE 16th December 2021
SUBJECT Revision requested for EGY-D-21-06511
TITLE Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants

Dr. Kalogirou
Editor in chief
Energy

Dear *Dr. Kalogirou*,

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewers. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript. The manuscript " Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants", wrote by Dr. Patricia Palenzuela, Dr. Lidia Roca, Dr. Faisal Asfand, Dr. Kumar Patchigolla, has been modified according to the suggestions made by Reviewer #3. The minor revisions have been highlighted in yellow.

We look forward to receive your comments on the revised document.

Yours faithfully

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Patricia Palenzuela'.

Patricia Palenzuela

Corresponding author:

Patricia Palenzuela
CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería. Ctra.de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain - Tel.: +35 950387900 Ext. 909, Fax: +34 950365015
ppalenzuela@psa.es – www.ciemat.es / www.psa.es

CORREO ELECTRÓNICO: ELECTRONIC MAIL:

ppalenzuela@psa.es

APTDO. DE CORREOS 22
E-04200 TABERNAS, ALMERÍA (SPAIN)
TEL.: +34 950387900 EXT. 909
FAX: +34 950365015

Corrections for Manuscript EGY-D-21-06511

Authors: Patricia Palenzuela, Lidia Roca, Faisal Asfand, Kumar Patchigolla

Title: Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants

The authors gratefully acknowledge the corrections, comments and recommendations that have been provided to us by the reviewer. We really appreciate the time and effort spent in reviewing this manuscript. All changes in the manuscript are highlighted in yellow.

Response to Reviewer #3:

1. Hybrid cooling systems have been shown as a potential solution for water consumption reduction in concentrating solar power plants. The authors had tested a hybrid cooling pilot-scale installed at Plataforma solar de Almaria experimentally. The results obtained had been discussed with illustrations using figures. The authors had concluded that the parallel configuration yielded better results in all the cases tested. I commend the authors for the provided responses to some of the issues raised in the first review. However, the under listed need to be corrected: The authors concluded that the most favorable configuration at all tested conditions is parallel with a split ratio of 50%. The authors did not state the ambient temperature. Minor revision recommended

Sorry for the misunderstanding but we did not realize in the previous revision that the ambient temperature shown in conclusion 1 was not correct (according to the results shown in Table 5). Now, we have corrected it and we have added the right one (18-23 °C) in conclusion 1 of the manuscript. We hope that now we are addressing your comment rightly.

Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants

Patricia Palenzuela^{1,*}, Lidia Roca^{1,4}, Faisal Asfand², Kumar Patchigolla³

¹CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería-CIESOL, Ctra.de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain.

²The School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield, Huddersfield, HD1 3DH, UK

³Centre for Thermal Energy and Materials, School of Water Energy and Environment, Cranfield University, Cranfield, Bedfordshire MK43 0AL, UK

*Corresponding author, patricia.palenzuela@psa.es, Tel.: +34 950 387800. Ext. 909

Abstract

The new challenge of the European Commission is to limit water consumption in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants, especially significant in the cooling process. Hybrid cooling systems are presented as a potential solution to achieve water consumption reduction since they also avoid a high penalty of efficiency loss in the power block. In this work, a hybrid cooling pilot plant installed at Plataforma Solar de Almería is evaluated experimentally. The system has been tested under different ambient and operating conditions to analyze their influence on the water and electricity consumption. The results reveal that significant water savings were achieved in comparison with the conventional only-wet configuration. Concretely, a maximum water consumption saving of 67% was found at high ambient temperatures (between 25 and 30 °C) and for a thermal load of 80% when a hybrid configuration was used. The optimal operating strategies that achieve a tradeoff between low water and electricity consumption have been identified by two efficiency indexes: the specific electricity and water consumption. The parallel configuration was the optimal one in most of the cases. At high ambient temperatures and 80% thermal load, the electricity and water consumptions of this configuration were 0.033 kW_e/kW_{th} and 0.071 L/kW_{th}, respectively.

Keywords: Hybrid Cooling, Pilot Plant, Water Consumption Saving, Experimental Characterization, Optimal operating strategies

1. Introduction

Water consumption in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants can reach values of up to 3000 m³/GW_e [1]. These plants are usually implemented in those locations with high Direct Normal Irradiance but where at the same time there is a significant water scarcity, so it is of extreme importance to reduce their water consumption. The condensation of the exhaust steam is the main source of water consumption, and it can be addressed by dry or wet cooling method.

1 Wet cooling is accomplished using two methods: once-through or evaporative wet cooling. Once-
2 through uses cold water, usually from the sea, so it allows relatively low condensation
3 temperatures, and is one of the most preferred cooling methods in terms of thermal efficiency of
4 the power cycle. However, its main drawback is the large volume of water that it uses and the
5 pollution threat to aquatic life due to the seawater extraction process and to the return of seawater
6 at a higher temperature [2]. Evaporative wet cooling is the most common method in CSP plants
7 since it relies on the wet bulb temperature and thus, leads to higher efficiency for the power block.
8 Its main problem is the requirement of a constant supply of fresh water due to the water
9 evaporation, a situation which is more aggravated in arid regions [3]. An example of the water
10 consumption is provided by a wet-cooled CSP plant located in the Mojave Desert, California,
11 which consumes about 3 m³/MWh [1]. This high amount of water makes CSP plants
12 unsustainable for such regions. Another problem of this kind of cooling systems is the generation
13 of a visible plume when the saturated exhaust air from the wet cooling tower (WCT) mixes with
14 dry and cold ambient air, especially in winter ([4–7]). It induces phenomena like fog, corrosion,
15 moisture, and darkness in the surrounding area that contribute to social concerns and, in the case
16 of CSP plants, to a possible decrease in the optical efficiency of the solar collector mirrors closest
17 to the cooling tower.

28 Dry cooling systems rely on dry bulb temperature and such plants have little or no water
29 consumption. The water consumption in a dry-cooled CSP plant can be reduced by about 95%
30 compared to wet cooling systems (having consumptions of about 0.30-0.34 m³/MWh [8]). The
31 typical examples are the Air Cooled Condensers (ACC) although there is an improved version of
32 this technology called Air Cooled Heat Exchanger (ACHE). In comparison with ACC, a power
33 plant with ACHE can produce 1% more electricity per year than the same plant with an ACC
34 system [9]. The main drawback of dry cooling systems is the higher capital costs and their
35 significant reduction in the power output (by up to 10% [1]) due to the higher condensation
36 temperature required compared to wet cooling systems and to the high electricity consumption
37 from the operation of the fans, especially at high ambient temperatures. Many efforts have been
38 made to increase the efficiency of dry cooling systems to the level of wet cooling systems [10],
39 but still there is a small percentage of these systems installed at CSP plants.

49 Several studies on the comparison between dry and wet cooling systems in CSP plants can be
50 found in the literature. Poullikas et al. [11] presented a comparative overview of evaporative
51 WCTs and ACC for the Rankine cycle of CSP plants. The comparison was performed considering
52 the overall plant's water requirements, the plant's efficiency, the plant's capital cost and the
53 plant's electricity unit cost. The authors concluded that, although ACC systems offer significant
54 reductions in water consumption against WCTs, their integration results in the overall plant's

1 efficiency reduction between 1-5% and increase in the overall capital costs ranging from 1% to
2 4%. This could lead to an increase in the net electricity unit cost between 2% and 9%, depending
3 on the CSP technology. Blanco-Marigorta et al. [12] also carried out a comparison between dry
4 and wet cooling technology for a CSP plant but in this case by means of an exergy analysis. They
5 found that the use of an ACC is not an efficient solution from an exergetic point of view for the
6 operation at low turbine exhaust pressures, although they are more competitive at higher
7 pressures.
8
9

10
11
12 Hybrid cooling (HC) systems are presented as a potential solution in CSP plants to cope with the
13 disadvantages of each conventional cooling method. They can reduce the water consumption by
14 up to an 80% [9] compared to wet-cooled CSP plants and enhance the performance in warm
15 weather compared to dry-cooled CSP plants [13]. Several studies on HC integrated into thermal
16 power plants can be found in the literature. Most of them are based on modelling and simulation
17 and aim for the evaluation of the performance of the thermal power plant with the HC system in
18 terms of power generation, water consumption reduction and costs. He et al. [14] developed a 1-D
19 model to predict the annual performance and water consumption of three different cooling
20 systems integrated into a geothermal power plant: a natural draft Dry Cooling Tower, a natural
21 draft WCT and a HC system. The simulations were performed taking the weather data for
22 Birdsville, Australia. From the results, it was found that water savings of 70% can be achieved
23 using the HC system in comparison with the WCT for every MW of heat rejection. In the case of
24 Zhai and Rubin [15], the authors carried out the assessment of the performance, water
25 consumption and costs for a HC system integrated into a coal or a natural-gas-fired power plant
26 with and without carbon capture and storage. The HC system was comprised of a wet-cooled
27 condenser and an ACC connected in parallel. The cost model considered the total annualized cost
28 and total levelized cost of electricity. From these results, the authors found reductions of roughly
29 91% in the water use for the HC system, but an increase of 3-5% of the Levelized Cost of
30 Electricity was observed. The paper concluded that the overall costs would be minimized if the
31 wet cooling system of the HC operated at a 30% of the total cooling load during hot periods. Hu
32 et al. [16] developed a model for a 660 MW steam power plant that integrates a HC system
33 consisting of ACC in series with a WCT. They investigated the heat transfer phenomena and the
34 water and power consumption for three operation modes: only-dry, only-wet and HC modes,
35 with respect to the change in the ambient temperature and relative humidity. It was found that at
36 high ambient temperatures and low relative humidity no benefits were observed for the HC mode
37 since the system operated as an only-wet cooling system. However, at an ambient temperature of
38 0 °C, the results were very favorable for the HC operation mode, with a 46.47% less water
39 consumption in comparison to only-wet and 45.84% less power fan consumption in comparison
40 to the only-dry operation mode. Dehaghani et al. [17] developed computational models to predict
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 the water saving of a thermal power plant located in Iran in the case that the current WCT was
2 modified by the use of a HC system (parallel wet and dry cooling system). The results were very
3 promising showing a 9.4% lower water consumption after the modifications and 64.6% less fan
4 power consumption if a high-precision air flow regulation method was used (fans with variable
5 frequency drives). Tang et al [18] evaluated the performance of a steam power plant with a HC
6 system, consisting in an ACC in parallel with a WCT, at different operating conditions (ambient
7 temperature, relative humidity, heat load). They concluded that the condensation through the
8 ACC was the best option at the following combinations of ambient temperature and thermal load:
9 16 °C/300 MW, 24 °C/225 MW and 31°C/150 MW. At higher ambient temperatures, the steam
10 condensation should be prioritized through the WCT. On the other hand, the authors of the present
11 paper [19] carried out the theoretical assessment of the best configurations of a HC system
12 integrated into a CSP plant in terms of power generation and water reduction. For this approach,
13 a model of the power block of a CSP plant (Andasol-1 type) which integrates a HC system was
14 implemented in Thermoflex software. The simulation of different configurations of the HC
15 system (composed of an ACHE and a WCT) was carried out: series, parallel, series-parallel and
16 parallel-series and for each one the water consumption and the net power generation were
17 determined. It was found that the most favorable configuration in terms of water saving was
18 series-parallel, resulting in 50% reduction of water consumption when compared to the only-wet
19 cooling option. For this configuration, a 2.5% higher power generation resulted compared to only-
20 dry cooling option. Other authors have investigated hybrid cooling towers (HCT), in which the
21 dry and wet cooling systems are integrated into the same tower. Rezaei et al. [20] developed a
22 model of a HCT able to operate in parallel or series configurations. The HCT included dry and
23 wet sections, being the dry section composed of several compact air-cooled exchangers. Finally,
24 Wei et al. [21] investigated the effect of ambient conditions over the performance of a natural
25 draft HCT and compared it with a natural draft dry cooling tower. It was found that the operation
26 of this hybrid system was more flexible than the natural draft dry cooling tower under variable
27 environmental conditions.
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45

46 Regarding experimental studies, there is limited research work on HC systems tested in real
47 environment. The existing ones are based on experiments at lab-scale [22,23]. In one of these
48 studies [23], promising results were found when the HC system was selected instead of a
49 conventional wet cooling system, resulting in 35% less water consumption. These results further
50 demonstrate the need for experiments at pilot-scale in order to provide reliable data for industry.
51 In addition, the urgent need to find the best operational strategies in HC systems that reduce the
52 water requirements in CSP plants is crucial. From the theoretical work presented above, only the
53 one presented by the authors of this paper [19] has considered the integration of a HC system into
54 a CSP plant. This paper complements the previous theoretical study by an exhaustive
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 experimental analysis of a pilot scale HC system installed at the Plataforma Solar de Almería
2 (PSA), in Tabernas (Almería), Spain. This system was manufactured and then installed at PSA
3 under the framework of an EU H2020 project on Water Saving for Concentrated Solar Power
4 (WASCOP). The pilot HC system consists of an ACHE and a WCT, both sharing a surface
5 condenser that is coupled with a steam generator driven by a solar field. The steam generator
6 generates low-pressure steam (pressure between 82 and 200 mbar) with similar conditions to those
7 obtained in the exhaust steam from the power block of a CSP plant. The HC pilot plant is flexible
8 and allows the HC operation in different configurations like series, parallel, only-wet and only-
9 dry. From the results obtained from the experimental assessment¹, the optimal configurations of
10 the HC system in terms of water and electricity consumption under a wide range of operating
11 (change in the thermal load) and environmental conditions (change in the ambient temperature)
12 has been obtained.

2. Description of the test facility

23 The HC pilot plant is located at PSA, which is the largest concentrating solar technology research,
24 development and test center in Europe and is a division of the Centro de Investigaciones
25 Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT). PSA is located in Tabernas (Latitude
26 31.10 N and Longitude 2.36 W) in the South of Spain. A Typical Meteorological Year for
27 Tabernas has been obtained using Meteornom software and the resulting monthly ambient
28 temperature throughout a typical year (2005) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Average monthly data of ambient temperature at PSA-CIEMAT

52 The HC pilot plant was designed and manufactured by the French company Hammon D'Hondt.
53 The company carried out a cost-effective optimization in order to minimize the initial CAPEX
54 for the pilot plant through equipment sharing. As a result, the design that was decided was that

60 ¹ Based on experiments carried out at PSA-CIEMAT

considering a hybrid cooler composed by an ACHE and a WCT sharing the surface condenser. The design allows flexibility to test WCT and an ACHE separately (only-wet, only-dry) or in series/parallel configurations. Fig. 2 shows the simplified schematic diagram of this pilot plant that consists of three main circuits: heating, exchange and cooling.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT

2.1. The heating circuit

In the heating circuit, hot water flows inside the tube bundles of a steam generator (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 (b)) with water, coming from a condensate tank, flows inside the shell side of this steam generator. Heat is then transferred from the hot water at high pressure in the tubes to the water at low pressure in the shell and subsequently steam is generated. Hot water is provided from a storage system, which is connected to a 300 kW_{th} flat-plate solar field (see Fig. 3 (a)) by means of a heat exchanger through which the thermal energy is transferred. For the sake of brevity, no further details about the solar field are given but further information can be found in Chorak et al [24]. The water flow rate inside the tube bundles of the steam generator (FT-005) is controlled using a Proportional, Integral and Derivative (PID) controller that uses the input to the variable frequency drive of Pump 4 (SC-006 in Fig. 2) as a control signal. On the other hand, the hot water inlet temperature (TT-010) is controlled at the desired value by the aperture of Valve 3. A PID controller acts over the aperture of this valve to mix the hot water from the storage system with the colder water coming from the steam generator. By controlling hot water flow rate and inlet temperature in the steam generator, different steam flow rates can be evaluated in the pilot plant. Therefore, it allows the operation of the HC system at different thermal loads, simulating its integration into a real CSP plant that is usually under partial load conditions due to the solar radiation variability.

Fig. 3. HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT: a) flat-plate collectors of the heating circuit, b) steam generator: hot water inlet (1) and outlet (2).

2.2. The exchange circuit

In the exchange circuit, a vacuum system (Pump 5 in Fig. 2) connected to a surface condenser allows choosing the desired vacuum pressure in the circuit by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) (in the range of 82-200 mbar). The steam generated flows into the surface condenser (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 4) where it is condensed while releasing the condensation heat to the cooling water circulating inside the tube bundle, which is in turn heated. The condensate from the surface condenser flows by gravity to a small deposit and it is then pumped to a condensate tank. The variable frequency drive of Pump 2 (SC-005 in Fig. 2) maintains the condensate level (LT-001 in Fig. 2) inside such deposit. Finally, water inside the condensate tank is pumped to the steam generator through Pump 3, closing the exchange circuit. This pump is turned on/off to maintain the level of liquid inside the steam generator (LT-002 in Fig. 2) at the desired value. Technical data for the steam generator and the surface condenser can be found in Table 1.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT, exchange circuit: (a) steam generator (1) and surface condenser (2), (b) surface condenser (1), condensate tank (2) and small deposit under the surface condenser (3).

2.3. The cooling circuit

The cooling circuit is composed of an ACHE and a WCT (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 5). Cooling water coming from both towers is pumped to the tube bundle of the surface condenser where it is heated by the heat transferred by condensation of the steam generated by the steam generator. Then, the heated cooling water flows back to the hybrid cooler to repeat the cooling process. The aperture of Valves 1 and 2 are modified to choose the desired configuration (see Table 2 and Fig. 2): only-dry, only-wet, series or parallel. In addition, a split ratio (defined as the wet fraction) can be selected in parallel configuration. The water flow rate in the tube bundle of the surface condenser (FT-003 in Fig. 2) is controlled using a PID controller that uses the variable frequency drive of Pump 1 (SC-004 Fig. 2) as control signal to maintain the nominal operating conditions despite the different head losses existing in each configuration. On the other hand, the variable frequency drives of the fans in both cooling towers (SC-001, SC-002 and SC-003 in Fig. 2) are used as control variables to maintain the inlet temperature to the surface condenser (TT-005 Fig. 2) at the desired value. Although most of the water in the cooling circuit recirculates, a small percentage of water evaporates in the WCT and must be replaced. A float valve installed in the WCT basin allows filling it with make-up water when the water level goes down. The make-up water consumed by the WCT is measured by a flow meter located at the inlet of this cooling tower (FT-004). Technical data of the cooling systems can be found in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Cooling circuit in the HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT. WCT (1) and ACHE (2)

Table 1
 Technical data of the equipment in the cooling and exchange circuits.

Steam generator

	Thermal power @42°C	80 kW _{th}
	Tube side	Hot water
	Shell side	Cold water/Steam
Surface condenser		
	Thermal power @42°C	80 kW _{th}
	Tube side	Water
	Shell side	Steam
WCT		
	Thermal power	204 kW _{th}
	Evaporation	0.28 m ³ /h
ACHE		
	Capacity	204 kW _{th}
	Exchange surface	617.58 m ²
	Power consumption	5.67 kW _e

Table 2
Configurations in the cooling circuit (see valve positions I and II in Fig. 2)

Configuration	Valve positions	
	Valve 1	Valve 2
Only-dry	II	II
Only-wet	-	I
Series	I	II
Parallel split ratio	II	Between I and II to achieve the desired split ratio

3. Methodology

3.1. Test campaign

The test campaign was designed to evaluate the different configurations of the HC system as a function of the ambient and operating conditions. Table 3 shows the range of variation for all of the variables. A total of 54 experiments were conducted in the year 2020 and 2021 and they were designed as follows (a flow chart showing the design is also depicted in Fig. 6):

- Three ambient temperature ranges were selected in order to cover the different seasons of the year in Tabernas (Almería). Note that these ranges are also typically found in other locations at the South of Europe. Here, ambient temperature between 10 and 15 °C represents the operation of the HC system in winter, ambient temperature between 18 and 23 °C represents the operation of the HC system in spring and autumn and ambient temperature between 25 and 30 °C represents the operation of the HC system in summer (see Figure 1).
- For each ambient temperature range, three thermal loads of the surface condenser were tested; a partial load of 60%, which corresponds to a thermal power between 120-125 kW_{th}; a partial load of 80%, which corresponds to a thermal power between 170- 175 kW_{th} and nominal conditions (i.e., thermal load of 100%) that corresponds to a thermal load

1 between 200-225 kW_{th}. It is important to highlight that the values selected for the thermal
2 load are not as important as the analysis of the influence of the variation of the thermal
3 load in the selection of the most suitable configuration.
4

- 5 • For each ambient temperature range and for the three thermal loads, configurations only-
6 dry (DC), only-wet (WC), series (SS) and parallel were tested. In the case of DC, WC
7 and SS, the maximum cooling flow rate (24 m³/h) circulates through both cooling towers.
8 In the case of parallel configurations, three split ratios were tested by the use of Valves 1
9 and 2 of cooling circuit (see Table 2 and Fig. 2): 25%, 50% and 75% for configurations
10 P25, P50 and P75, respectively. In the case of P25, FT-001 is 6 m³/h and FT-002 is 18
11 m³/h; in the case of P50, FT-001 and FT-002 it is 12 m³/h and in the case of P75, FT-001
12 it is 18 m³/h and for FT-002 it is 6 m³/h. The set point of cooling flow rate was established
13 in the variable frequency drive of pump 1 (SC-004 in Fig. 2).
14
- 15 • In all tests, the temperature of the steam produced by the steam generator (TT-008 in Fig.
16 2) was maintained at 45 °C. This temperature represents the condensation temperature
17 (i.e. the exhaust steam temperature) in a CSP plant. This value has been established
18 accounting that the typical condensation temperatures in CSP plants in the South of
19 Europe, where the large-scale plant market is mostly concentrated [25], are between 0.063
20 and 0.2 bar [12]. It was controlled by establishing a set point of vacuum pressure in the
21 PLC of the vacuum system (Pump 5 in Fig. 2).
22
- 23 • In all tests, the hot water flow rate flowing inside the tube bundle of the steam generator
24 (FT 005 in Fig. 2) was kept at 9.75 L/s. On the other hand, the hot water inlet temperature
25 in the steam generator (TT-010) varied between 68 °C and 76.5 °C to assure the thermal
26 loads mentioned above.
27
- 28 • Finally, the temperature at the inlet of the surface condenser (TT-005 in Fig. 2) was
29 established in all cases at 33 °C (i.e., the design temperature of this equipment). This was
30 established by the control of the variable frequency drives of both cooling towers (SC-
31 001, SC-002 and SC-003 in Fig. 2). In the case of series configuration, as the cooling
32 water is cooled firstly through the ACHE and then through the WCT, the temperatures at
33 the outlet of the ACHE (TT-003 in Fig. 2) and WCT (TT-006 in Fig. 2) were maintained
34 at 36 °C and 33 °C, respectively.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 6. Flow chart of the designed test campaign

Table 3
Range of variation of the ambient and operating variables

Variable	Range of operation
Ambient temperature, T_{amb}	(10-30) °C
Thermal load, TL	(60-100) %
Cooling water flow rate through the ACHE, FT-002	(6-24) m ³ /h
Cooling water flow rate through the WCT, FT-001	(6-24) m ³ /h
Hot water inlet temperature in the steam generator, TE-WAS-010	(68-73.5) °C
Variable frequency drives (VFD) of the ACHE, SC-002 and SC003	(11-98)%
Variable frequency drive (VFD) of the WCT, SC-001	(21-100)%

It is important to ensure steady state conditions during the operation of the HC, especially for the steam flow rate generated by the steam generator and in the case of make-up water consumed by the WCT (FT-004 in Fig. 2). In the case of the generated steam, the level of the steam generator (LT-002 in Fig. 2) was maintained at a stable level of around 330 mm to assure that the tube bundles were completely flooded. The water circulation from the surface condenser to the condensate tank was also kept as steady as possible. For that purpose, the level in the small deposit at the outlet of the surface condenser (LT-001 in Fig. 2) was maintained around 200 mm.

The data was logged every second and the average value of each variable was determined in a steady stage period of between 15-20 minutes. An error analysis was performed considering the measurement uncertainties of all the instruments. In the case of the indirect parameters an uncertainty propagation analysis was carried out to quantify the accuracy of the results. For this purpose, a tool from the Engineering Equation Solver software described in NIST Technical Note 1297 was used [26]. The measurement uncertainties of all measured variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4
Measurement uncertainty of the direct variables

Parameter	Measurement uncertainty
Electricity consumed by the WCT, ACHE and pump	1%
1	
Make-up water consumed by the WCT	$\pm 0.5\%$ of F.S ^a + 2.5% o.r ^b
Condensate mass flow rate	$\pm 0.2\%$ o.r ^b
Saturated steam pressure	$\pm 0.3\%$ o.r ^b + 0.8% of URL ^a
Temperatures	$0.3+0.005 \cdot T^c$

^aF.S = full scale. It is 10 for FT-WAS-004 and 1.1 bar for PT-001

^bo.r = of reading

^cis the value of the temperature in °C

3.2. Assessment of the hybrid configurations

The HC configurations were evaluated by determining the improvements achieved in terms of electricity consumption reduction, in comparison to only-dry operation mode (i.e. $(ec_{DC} - ec_{HC})/ec_{DC}$) and in terms of water consumption reduction, in comparison with only-wet operation mode (i.e. $(wc_{WC} - wc_{HC})/wc_{WC}$). ec_{HC} and ec_{DC} are the electricity consumptions of the hybrid and DC configurations, respectively, and wc_{HC} and wc_{WC} are the water consumptions of the hybrid and WC configurations, respectively. The results obtained at different thermal loads and ambient temperatures are shown and explained in section 4.

The following sections describe the calculations of the electricity and water consumptions.

3.1.1. Electricity consumption

The electricity consumption (ec) is measured with an electrical energy meter (CEM-C21) installed in the electrical distribution panel of the facility that provides the instantaneous power consumption of the Pump 1 and for the WCT and ACHE fans. This consumption depends on the percentage applied to the corresponding VFD, as can be observed in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Electricity consumption measurements at different percentages applied to the VFDs.

The total measured electricity consumption is the sum of each one of the contributions (Pump 1, WCT and ACHE fans). It is important to highlight that the operating point of Pump 1 in the

1 experimental campaign described in this paper corresponds to values in the VFD, SC-004,
2 between 91% and 97%. In the case of the ACHE operation, the values in the experimental
3 campaign analyzed in this paper cover the whole range of SC-002 and SC-003 depicted in Fig.
4 7, while in the case of the WCT operation, the maximum percentage required in SC-001 was
5 40%.
6
7

8 9 3.1.2. Water consumption

10 As already mentioned, wc is measured by a flow meter located at the inlet of the make-up water
11 pipe (FT-004 in Fig. 2). As it is evaluated when steady-state conditions are reached, the make-up
12 flow can be considered to correspond to the water evaporated in the WCT.
13
14
15
16

17 3.3. Efficiency calculation and selection of optimal configurations

18 Two efficiency indexes that determine the specific electricity energy consumption (SEC) and the
19 specific water consumption (SWC) are proposed to decide which is the optimal configuration
20 according to the ambient and operating conditions. There must be a trade-off between the water
21 and the electricity consumption, considering also the relation of these values with the thermal
22 power. In other words, optimal configurations will be the ones that allow reducing as much as
23 possible the water and electricity consumptions per kW_{th} used to condense the available steam.
24 These indexes are thus a measurement of the efficiency of the system since they relate the
25 consumptions that penalize the process with the rejected heat, which would be in turn related with
26 the electricity produced in a real turbine. The calculation of these indexes is as follows:
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35

$$36 SEC \left(\frac{kW_e}{kW_{th}} \right) = \frac{ec}{TP}, \quad (1)$$

$$37 SWC \left(\frac{L/h}{kW_{th}} \right) = \frac{wc}{TP}, \quad (2)$$

38 where ec is the electricity consumption measured in kW_e , wc is the water consumption in L/h and
39 TP is the thermal power of the surface condenser measured in kW_{th} . It is defined as the heat
40 transfer rate by condensation of the steam generated and can be determined by Eq.**Error!**
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 **Reference source not found.:**

$$49 TP = \dot{m}_s \lambda_{cond} + \dot{m}_c (h_{l,sat} - h_c), \quad (3)$$

50 where \dot{m}_s is the steam mass flow rate generated by the steam generator, λ_{cond} is the latent heat
51 of condensation at the pressure measured in PT-001 (see Fig. 2), \dot{m}_c is the condensate mass flow
52 rate at the outlet of the surface condenser, $h_{l,sat}$ is the specific enthalpy of saturated liquid in the
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

surface condenser at pressure PT-001 and h_c is the specific enthalpy of the subcooled condensate leaving the surface condenser, at the temperature TT-007 (see Fig. 2) and pressure PT-001.

Notice that, as the evaluation of the HC is performed at steady state conditions, the steam entering the surface condenser is completely condensed, so it can be assumed that $\dot{m}_s = \dot{m}_c$. In addition, the VFD of Pump 2 is regulated to maintain LT-001 at a steady-state value, so the mass flow rate at the outlet of the surface condenser (\dot{m}_c) is that measured in FT-006 (see Fig. 2).

The optimal configurations are obtained by a cost function, J_{ijk} , which is evaluated for each configuration, i , thermal load, j , and ambient temperature, k , being $i=\{WC,P75,P50,P25,SS,DC\}$, $j=\{TL-60,TL-80,TL-100\}$ and $k=\{(10-15), (18-23), (25-30)\}$ °C:

$$J_{ijk} = \alpha_1 \cdot \frac{SEC_{ijk} - SEC_{jk}^{min}}{SEC_{jk}^{max} - SEC_{jk}^{min}} + \alpha_2 \cdot \frac{SWC_{ijk} - SWC_{jk}^{min}}{SWC_{jk}^{max} - SWC_{jk}^{min}}, \quad (4)$$

$$SEC_{jk}^{min} = \min\{SEC_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}, \quad (5)$$

$$SEC_{jk}^{max} = \max\{SEC_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}, \quad (6)$$

where SEC and SWC are normalized to bring all values into the range [0,1] and α_1 and α_2 are weighting factors to tune the importance of each term in relation to the other. In this case, the values established for these factors are: $\alpha_1=1$ and $\alpha_2=1.2$, because the priority is to reduce the water consumption. The optimal value for each load and ambient temperature range, θ_{jk} , corresponds to that configuration that gives the minimum value of J :

$$\theta_{jk} = \min_i \{J_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}. \quad (7)$$

4. Results

4.1 Variation of the electricity consumption

This section shows the variation of the electricity consumption and of the temperatures in the cooling circuit (i.e., the inlet and outlet temperatures from the ACHE and WCT) with the TL and with the ambient temperature for the different HC configurations (see Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). TL-100 corresponds to the operation at thermal load 100%, TL-80 to the operation at thermal load 80% and TL-60 to the operation at thermal load 60%. In addition, this section shows the percentages of ec reduction of the HC configurations in comparison to configuration only-dry (the one with the highest electricity consumption) for the different TL and ambient temperature ranges (see Table 5). The errors obtained from the uncertainty propagation analysis are also shown in this table together with the percentage results.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 8. Effect of the thermal load on the electricity consumption for a) T_{amb} (10-15) °C; b) (18-23) °C and c) (25-30) °C. All the errors are represented as error bars

Fig. 9. Temperatures in the cooling circuit at different ambient temperature ranges (H: (25-30) °C, M: (18-23) °C, L: (13-15) °C) at a TL (a) 100%, (b) 80% and (c) 60%. The maximum error of the temperature measurements is 0.5 °C (see Table 1).

As observed in Fig. 8, the value of ec increased in all configurations with the thermal load and with the ambient temperature. The increase with the thermal load is explained by the rise in the cooling water temperatures at the inlet of the WCT and ACHE (TT-001 and TT-002, respectively)

1 when the TP in the surface condenser increases, as can be seen in Fig. 9. Such a temperature rise
2 leads to a higher percentage required in SC-001, SC-002 and SC-003 to achieve the desired
3 temperature at the inlet of the surface condenser (33 °C). Likewise, higher percentages in SC-001,
4 SC-002 and SC-003 are directly related to a higher electricity consumption of the cooling system,
5 as indicated in Fig. 7. On the other hand, the higher the ambient temperature the higher the
6 percentage needed in the VFD of both cooling towers to achieve the cooling requirements, which
7 leads to a rise in the ec , as seen in Fig. 7. This ec increase is especially significant in the case of
8 the ACHE (configuration DC), as seen in Fig. 8, since in this case the ec increases at a higher rate
9 the higher the percentage used in SC-002 and SC-003 is. For the rest of configurations, it can be
10 seen that at low and medium ambient temperatures, there are no significant differences between
11 them in terms of ec , for the different thermal loads. It can be seen that WC, SS, P75 and P25 have
12 similar ec , and the configuration P50 was the one with the lowest electricity consumptions. It is
13 important to highlight that, although a lower ec for configuration WC is expected compared with
14 the HC configurations, the head losses in the cooling circuit for this configuration are higher than
15 for the others, which led to a higher electricity consumed by Pump 1. At high ambient
16 temperatures, the differences in ec between configurations became more significant, especially at
17 higher thermal loads. At TL-80, the configurations that showed the highest ec were P25 and SS
18 and at TL-100, P50 and SS.

19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31 The results shown in Table 5 can help select the most suitable configurations in terms of ec
32 reduction compared to the conventional only-dry cooling system. As it can be seen, the ec
33 reduction of configurations P50, P75, P25, WC and SS with respect the configuration for only-
34 dry was higher the higher the thermal load and ambient temperature were. This is a reasonable
35 result given the reasons mentioned before regarding the significant effect of both variables (TL
36 and ambient temperature) in the ec of the ACHE. At low ambient temperatures (i.e., between 10
37 and 15 °C) and the lowest TL (TL-60), the percentage of reduction in the ec with respect to the
38 operation with configuration only-dry was not very significant, and the highest value was 11.7%
39 for configuration P25. When the TL was increased up to 80%, the percentage of ec reduction
40 compared to only-dry became more significant for some configurations, thus P50 showed the
41 higher ec reduction (24.0%), followed by P25 that achieved a percentage of ec reduction of
42 18.9%. At nominal conditions (TL-100), the HC operation allowed an important ec reduction
43 compared to the conventional only-dry operation and the same configurations as before (P50 or
44 P25) achieved higher improvements in terms of ec (the percentages of reduction were 34.7% and
45 28.6%, respectively). At medium ambient temperatures (i.e., between 18 and 23 °C), the
46 percentages of ec reduction increased with respect to the operation at low ambient temperatures,
47 being more pronounced at higher TL s. In the case of TL-60, the recommended configuration in
48 terms of ec saving would be P50, since it showed the highest ec reduction (34.0%). At TL-80,
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

apart from P50 (whose percentage of *ec* reduction compared with DC was 46.7%), P75 also gave good results (40.0% of *ec* reduction), so these two HC configurations could be suitable in case *ec* is prioritized. At nominal load, the same HC configurations are recommended in terms of *ec* reduction. Finally, at high ambient temperatures (i.e. between 25 and 30 °C), the percentages of *ec* reduction in comparison with the only-dry configuration were the highest ones, achieving values close to 50%. Among the tests performed at the lowest *TL*, it was found that the operation with configurations P50, P75 and WC is recommended when a significant *ec* reduction is required compared with the conventional only-dry configuration. The percentages of reduction obtained were 44.4% for P50, 40.1% for P75 and 40.6% for WC.

Table 5
Percentages of electricity consumption reduction of the HC configurations with the associated errors in comparison to configuration only-dry for the different thermal loads and ambient temperature ranges

Configuration	Thermal Load	Ambient temperature ranges		
		(10-15) °C	(18-23) °C	(25-30) °C
WC	TL-60	(4.6±1.3)%	(22.4±1.1)%	(40.6±0.8)%
	TL-80	(11.2±1.3)%	(38.8±0.9)%	(52.7±0.7)%
	TL-100	(23.7±1.1)%	(53.8±0.7)%	(49.7±0.7)%
P75	TL-60	(8.1±1.2)%	(24.7±1.1)%	(40.1±0.8)%
	TL-80	(14.5±1.2)%	(40.0±0.8)%	(52.7±0.7)%
	TL-100	(25.8±1.1)%	(54.6±0.6)%	(49.7±0.7)%
P50	TL-60	(22.7±1.2)%	(34.0±0.9)%	(44.4±0.8)%
	TL-80	(24.0±1.1)%	(46.7±0.7)%	(46.4±0.8)%
	TL-100	(34.7±0.9)%	(59.4±0.6)%	(0.0±1.4)%
P25	TL-60	(15.4±1.2)%	(28.7±1.0)%	(28.8±1.0)%
	TL-80	(18.9±1.1)%	(38.6±0.9)%	(3.1±1.4)%
	TL-100	(28.6±0.9)%	(53.2±0.7)%	(1.4±1.4)%
SS	TL-60	(4.4±1.3)%	(22.2±1.1)%	(37.9±0.9)%
	TL-80	(10.7±1.3)%	(37.6±0.9)%	(25.2±1.1)%
	TL-100	(23.1±1.1)%	(50.6±0.7)%	(22.4±1.1)%

4.2 Variation of the water consumption

This section shows the variation of the water consumption of the HC at different TL and ambient temperature (see Fig. 10). In addition, it shows the percentages of wc reduction of the HC configurations in comparison to configuration only-wet, which can be found in Table 6.

Fig. 10. Effect of the thermal load on the water consumption for a) T_{amb} (10-15) °C; b) (18-23) °C and c) (25-30) °C. All the errors are represented as error bars

As observed in Fig. 10, w_c increased in all configurations with the thermal load, except in the case of configuration SS. This increase is due to the rise in the cooling water temperature at the inlet of the WCT with the thermal load (see Fig. 9). An increase in this cooling water temperature leads to a higher energy demand required to reduce the enthalpy of the water through the WCT to reach the desired 33 °C at the outlet. Then, the air flow rate must increase (by means of the VFD of the fan) in order to cover such energy demand, causing higher losses by evaporation and consequently higher water consumptions. In series configuration, w_c presented similar values at different TLs because the cooling water temperature at the inlet of the WCT (TT-001 in Fig. 9) was maintained at 36 °C. This makes the VFD of the fan work at similar operating conditions, as the air flow rate were then similar and therefore the losses by evaporation also.

Regarding the behaviour of the w_c with respect to the ambient temperature, it is expected that the water consumption in the WCT increases with increasing ambient temperature because the energy demand required to reduce the enthalpy of the water through the tower (and reach 33 °C at the outlet) depends on the air enthalpy difference between the outlet and the inlet. Since the air inlet enthalpy increases with the ambient temperature, the air flow rate must increase (by means of the VFD of the fan) in order to cover the energy demand, causing higher losses by evaporation (i.e., higher water consumptions). As seen in Fig. 10, this increase was observed in the case of configurations WC and P75. However, in the case of P50 and P25 configurations, the tendency was opposite to the previous cases and the w_c decreased with the ambient temperature. This fact is directly related to the cooling capacity of the WCT. When the WCT is operating with medium-low cooling flow rates (12 m³/h in the case of P50 and 6 m³/h in the case of P25) and the ambient

1 temperature and/or the water inlet enthalpy are low (i.e. partial loads), the temperature at the outlet
 2 of the WCT (TT-006 in Fig. 9) is under 33 °C because the minimum fan percentage (21%) is
 3 achieved. Therefore, the air mass flow in these cases is higher than needed in order to achieve the
 4 required operating conditions and the losses by evaporation are higher than expected. To
 5 understand this fact better, configuration P50 at TL-100 is taken as an example. At low ambient
 6 temperature, the VFD of the WCT was at the minimum value, and the outlet temperature of the
 7 WCT was lower than required, 30 °C. Then, it can be seen in Fig. 9 that the temperature difference
 8 between the inlet (TT-001) and the outlet of the WCT (TT-006) was higher at low ambient
 9 temperatures than at high ambient temperatures, which is directly related to the water
 10 consumption as explained previously.

11 In the case of SS configuration, as already mentioned, the water inlet temperature to the WCT is
 12 always maintained at 36 °C (TT-001 in Fig. 9), and a similar water consumption can be observed
 13 for the three ambient temperature ranges. This is caused because the temperature difference
 14 between the inlet and outlet temperatures in the WCT was low (only 3 °C), which led to a low
 15 required heat transfer to achieve this temperature difference through water evaporation.

16 The comparison between configurations was carried out by evaluating the water consumption
 17 reduction in the case of using a HC configuration instead of an only-wet configuration, which is
 18 the configuration with the highest wc. The values obtained together with the resulting errors from
 19 the uncertainty propagation analysis can be found in Table 6.

20 Table 6
 21 Percentages of water consumption reduction of the HC configurations with the associated errors
 22 in comparison to configuration only-wet for the different thermal loads and ambient temperature
 23 ranges.

Configuration	Thermal Load	Ambient temperature ranges		
		(10-15) °C	(18-23) °C	(25-30) °C
P75	TL-60	(26.2±9.9)%	(23.2±10.0)%	(24.2±9.1)%
	TL-80	(26.9±7.9)%	(23.0±8.02)%	(38.1±6.5)%
	TL-100	(27.9±7.1)%	(21.8±7.2)%	(23.6±6.7)%
P50	TL-60	(33.9±9.4)%	(22.8±10.0)%	(38.7±8.1)%
	TL-80	(33.6±7.4)%	(38.6±7.1)%	(51.6±5.8)%
	TL-100	(33.0±6.8)%	(41.6±6.1)%	(43.3±5.6)%
P25	TL-60	(50.2±8.3)%	(47.8±8.3)%	(56.9±7.0)%
	TL-80	(60.4±5.9)%	(59.7±5.9)%	(66.9±5.0)%
	TL-100	(58.2±5.4)%	(61.6±5.0)%	(61.3±4.7)%
	TL-60	(27.2±9.9)%	(25.6±9.8)%	(37.3±8.2)%

SS	TL-80	(44.3±6.8)%	(44.7±6.7)%	(52.8±5.7)%
	TL-100	(54.4±5.6)%	(57.9±5.2)%	(59.7±4.8)%

As expected, the highest w_c reduction was obtained from configuration P25 (66.9% at high ambient temperature and TL-80) since this is the configuration with the least use of the WCT, with only 6 m³/h of water flow rate through the WCT. On the opposite side, P75 was the HC configuration that makes the highest use of the WCT (18 m³/h of water flow rate) so it achieved the lowest water reduction in comparison to configuration only-wet (24.2% at medium ambient temperature and TL-60).

The water consumption reduction in configuration P25 increased with TL and ambient temperature between 50.2% and 66.9%, a considerable reduction that emphasizes the importance of combining wet and dry cooling to reduce the water consumption throughout the year and for all thermal loads. In the case of SS configuration, the percentages of water consumption reduction also increased with the ambient temperature and TL but it was more significant at TL-80 and TL-100 (between 44.7% and 59.7%). At low thermal load, TL-60, the percentage of increase was between 25.6% and 37.2%, which was closer to the values obtained with parallel configurations. The percentages of increase with configuration P50 were lower than in the previous cases and did not show a specific tendency with the ambient temperature and the TL because of the WCT cooling capacity limitation in some of the experiments, as explained previously. In the case of configuration P75, the percentages at different TL s and several ambient temperatures varied over a narrow range (between 21.8% and 27.9%), and did not follow a clear tendency because the water consumption in this configuration was closer to the one obtained with configuration only-wet.

4.2. Optimal configurations

Fig. 11 shows the results of SEC and SWC obtained for each one of the configurations, thermal loads and ambient temperature ranges. The maximum error obtained from the uncertainty analysis resulted of 0.0007 kW_e/kW_{th} and 0.11 L/h·kW_{th} for the SEC and SWC , respectively. The optimal configurations obtained are represented in bold type.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 11. *SWC* against *SEC* for each configuration, at different thermal loads and at different ambient temperature ranges (a) (10-15) °C, (b) (18-23) °C and (c) (25-30) °C. Optimal configurations are represented in bold type.

At low ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (a)), the best results were obtained from configuration P25 at TL-60 and TL-80. At this ambient temperature, the electricity consumption in the ACHE is low, so it is recommended to operate as much as possible with this configuration in order to reduce the water consumption. At TL-100, configuration P50 gave better results than P25, due to the difference of the electricity consumption between these two configurations. Configuration P25 resulted also the best one in the case of medium ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (b)), but it is also important to highlight that configuration P50 allowed to reduce the *SEC* even more at the expense of increasing the *SWC*. It is important to mention that for all ambient temperature ranges, the lowest specific consumptions were obtained operating at TL-100, which means that partial loads penalize the consumption per kW_{th}. In the case of high ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (c)), the specific consumptions increased, mainly because of the electricity consumption in the ACHE. For this reason, at high ambient temperatures it would be recommended to reduce the use of the ACHE, being the optimal configurations SS at TL-100 and P50 at TL-80 and TL-60.

5. Conclusions

This study deals with the assessment of the best operating strategies of a HC system in terms of reduction in the water and electricity consumptions in comparison with the conventional only-dry and only-wet cooling systems. An exhaustive experimental campaign has been carried out at a HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT, testing different configurations over a wide range of operating (different thermal loads) and ambient (different ambient temperatures) conditions. The results obtained from this study can help the CSP industry to invest in HC solutions at industrial scale, since it has been proven that there are strategies that allow to reach a trade-off between the water and the electricity consumption depending on the thermal load of the power block and on the ambient temperature. The main conclusions obtained from the experimental evaluation are given below:

- The most favorable configuration in terms of reduction in the electricity consumption at all tested conditions is a parallel one with a split ratio of 50%. For this configuration, a maximum reduction of 59.3% was obtained compared to the only-dry configuration, at nominal load (TL-100) and high ambient temperature (18-23 °C).
- Configuration parallel with a split ratio of 25% has shown the highest reduction in the water consumption when compared with a conventional only-wet configuration. A percentage of 66.9% was obtained when the pilot plant operated at a thermal load of 80% and the ambient temperature was between 25 and 30 °C.
- The assessment of the optimal operating strategies has been achieved by the evaluation of two efficiency indicators, which consider the relation of the water and electricity consumptions with the thermal power required to condensate the available steam. These efficiency indicators are the *SEC* and the *SWC*.
- At low ambient temperatures, the optimal strategy at partial loads (TL-80 and TL-100) is the operation with configuration parallel with split ratio of 25%. However, when the load is reduced to TL-60, it is recommended to change the strategy, and operate with configuration parallel with split ratio of 50%.
- At medium ambient temperatures, the best strategy is to operate with configuration parallel with a split ratio of 25% at all thermal loads.
- In the case of high ambient temperatures, the most favorable strategy at partial loads (TL-60 and TL-80) is the operation with configuration parallel with a split ratio of 50%. When the thermal load increases at TL-100, the strategy should be changed to

configuration series that provide an optimal trade-off between the water and electricity consumption.

Nomenclature

Symbols

TP	Thermal power, kW _{th}
Ec	Electricity consumption in the cooling circuit, kW _e
ec_{DC}	Electricity consumption in only-dry configuration, kW _e
ec_{HC}	Electricity consumption in a hybrid configuration, kW _e
ec_{WC}	Electricity consumption in only-wet configuration, kW _e
h_c	Specific enthalpy of the condensate, kJ/kg
$h_{l,sat}$	Specific enthalpy of the saturated liquid, kJ/kg
\dot{m}_c	Condensate mass flow rate (FT-006 in Fig. 2), kg/s
\dot{m}_s	Steam mass flow rate between the steam generator and the surface condenser, kg/s
SEC	Specific electric energy consumption, kW _e /kW _{th}
SWC	Specific water consumption, L/h·kW _{th}
T_{amb}	Ambient temperature, °C
TL	Thermal load, %
wc	Water consumption, L/h
wc_{HC}	Water consumption in a hybrid configuration, L/h
wc_{WC}	Water consumption in only-wet configuration, L/h

1 λ_{cond} Latent heat of condensation, kJ/kg

2
3
4 *Abbreviations*

5
6
7 ACC Air Cooled Condensers

8
9
10 ACHE Air Cooler Heat Exchanger

11
12
13 CIEMAT Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y
14 Tecnológicas

15
16
17 CSP Concentrated Solar Power

18
19
20 DC Only-dry

21
22
23 VFD Variable Frequency Drive

24
25
26 HC Hybrid cooling

27
28
29 HCT Hybrid cooling tower

30
31
32 PID Proportional, Integral and Derivative control

33
34
35 PLC Programmable Logic Controller

36
37
38 PSA Plataforma Solar de Almería

39
40
41 P25 Parallel with a split ratio of 25%

42
43
44 P50 Parallel with a split ratio of 50%

45
46
47 P75 Parallel with a split ratio of 75%

48
49
50 SS Series

51
52
53 WASCOP Water Saving for Concentrated Solar Power

54
55
56 WC Only-wet

57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Acknowledgments

We thank the Plataforma Solar de Almeria for providing access to its installations

References

- [1] K. Damerau, K. Williges, A.G. Patt, P. Gauché, Costs of reducing water use of concentrating solar power to sustainable levels : Scenarios for North Africa, *Energy Policy*. 39 (2011) 4391–4398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.04.059>.
- [2] S.W. Mohammed Ali, N. Vahedi, C. Romero, A. Oztekin, An optimization for water requirement in natural gas combined cycle power plants equipped with once-through and hybrid cooling systems and carbon capture unit, *Water-Energy Nexus*. 3 (2020) 117–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2020.08.001>.
- [3] M. Martín, M. Martín, Cooling limitations in power plants : Optimal multiperiod design of natural draft cooling towers, *Energy*. 135 (2017) 625–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.06.171>.
- [4] A. Corti, E. Carnevale, Environmental impact from wet plumes in combined-cycle power plants, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 18 (1998) 1049–1057. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-4311\(98\)00029-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-4311(98)00029-5).
- [5] S.K. Tyagi, A.K. Pandey, P.C. Pant, V. V. Tyagi, Formation, potential and abatement of plume from wet cooling towers: A review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 16 (2012) 3409–3429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.059>.
- [6] T.M.L. Wigley, P.R. Slawson, The effect of atmospheric conditions on the length of visible cooling tower plumes, *Atmos. Environ.* 9 (1975) 437–445.
- [7] X. Xu, S. Wang, Z. Ma, Evaluation of plume potential and plume abatement of evaporative cooling towers in a subtropical region, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 28 (2008) 1471–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2007.09.003>.
- [8] C. Turchi, K. Chuck, Water use in concentrating solar power (CSP), (2009). <http://www.swhydro.arizona.edu/renewable/presentations/thursday/turchi.pdf>.
- [9] A. Colmenar-Santos, D. Borge-Diez, C.P. Molina, M. Castro-Gil, Water consumption in solar parabolic trough plants : review and analysis of the southern Spain case, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 34 (2014) 565–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.03.042>.
- [10] K. Hooman, Z. Guan, H. Gurgenci, *Advances in dry cooling for concentrating solar thermal (CST) power plants*, Elsevier Ltd, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100516-3.00009-5>.
- [11] A. Poullikkas, I. Hadjipaschalis, G. Kourtis, A comparative overview of wet and dry cooling systems for Rankine cycle based CSP plants, *Trends Heat Mass Transf.* 13 (2013) 27–50.
- [12] A.M. Blanco-Marigorta, M. Victoria Sanchez-Henríquez, J.A. Peña-Quintana, Exergetic comparison of two different cooling technologies for the power cycle of a thermal power plant, *Energy*. 36 (2011) 1966–1972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2010.09.033>.
- [13] C. Kutscher, D. Costenaro, Assessment of evaporative cooling enhancement methods for air-cooled geothermal power plants, No. NREL/CP-550-32394. Natl. Renew. Energy Lab., Golden, CO.(US). (2002) 1–9. <http://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy02osti/32394.pdf>.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [14] S. He, H. Gurgenci, Z. Guan, K. Hooman, Z. Zou, Comparative study on the performance of natural draft dry, pre-cooled and wet cooling towers, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 99 (2016) 103–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.01.060>.
- [15] H. Zhai, E.S. Rubin, A techno-economic assessment of hybrid cooling systems for coal- and natural-gas-fired power plants with and without carbon capture and storage, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50 (2016) 4127–4134. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b00008>.
- [16] H. Hu, Z. Li, Y. Jiang, X. Du, Thermodynamic characteristics of thermal power plant with hybrid (dry/wet) cooling system, *Energy*. 147 (2018) 729–741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.01.074>.
- [17] S. Taghian Dehaghani, H. Ahmadikia, Retrofit of a wet cooling tower in order to reduce water and fan power consumption using a wet/dry approach, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 125 (2017) 1002–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.07.069>.
- [18] T. Tang, J. Xu, S. Jin, H. Wei, Study on Operating Characteristics of Power Plant with Dry and Wet Cooling Systems, *Energy Power Eng.* 05 (2013) 651–656. <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2013.54b126>.
- [19] F. Asfand, P. Palenzuela, L. Roca, A. Caron, C.-A. Lemarié, J. Gillard, P. Turner, K. Patchigolla, Thermodynamic performance and water consumption of hybrid cooling system configurations for concentrated solar power plants, *Sustainability*. 12 (2020) 1–19.
- [20] E. Rezaei, S. Shafiei, A. Abdollahnezhad, Reducing water consumption of an industrial plant cooling unit using hybrid cooling tower, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 51 (2010) 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2009.09.027>.
- [21] H. Wei, X. Huang, L. Chen, L. Yang, X. Du, Performance of a novel natural draft hybrid cooling tower for thermal power generation, *Energy Procedia*. 158 (2019) 5231–5237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.01.661>.
- [22] W. Asvapoositkul, M. Kuansathan, Comparative evaluation of hybrid (dry/wet) cooling tower performance, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 71 (2014) 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.06.023>.
- [23] M. Deziani, K. Rahmani, S.J. Mirrezaei Roudaki, M. Kordloo, Feasibility study for reduce water evaporative loss in a power plant cooling tower by using air to air heat exchanger with auxiliary fan, *Desalination*. 406 (2017) 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2015.12.007>.
- [24] A. Chorak, P. Palenzuela, D.C. Alarcón-Padilla, A. Ben Abdellah, Experimental characterization of a multi-effect distillation system coupled to a flat plate solar collector field: Empirical correlations, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 120 (2017) 298–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.03.115>.
- [25] W. Weiss, M. Spörk-Dür, Solar heat worldwide: Global market development and trends in 2020, 2021.
- [26] B.N. Taylor, C.E. Kuyatt, Guidelines for evaluating and expressing the uncertainty of NIST measurement results, 1994. <http://physics.nist.gov/TN1297>.

Experimental Assessment of a Pilot Scale Hybrid Cooling System for Water Consumption Reduction in CSP Plants

Patricia Palenzuela^{1,*}, Lidia Roca^{1,4}, Faisal Asfand², Kumar Patchigolla³

¹CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almería-CIESOL, Ctra.de Senés s/n, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain.

²The School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield, Huddersfield, HD1 3DH, UK

³Centre for Thermal Energy and Materials, School of Water Energy and Environment, Cranfield University, Cranfield, Bedfordshire MK43 0AL, UK

*Corresponding author, patricia.palenzuela@psa.es, Tel.: +34 950 387800. Ext. 909

Abstract

The new challenge of the European Commission is to limit water consumption in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants, especially significant in the cooling process. Hybrid cooling systems are presented as a potential solution to achieve water consumption reduction since they also avoid a high penalty of efficiency loss in the power block. In this work, a hybrid cooling pilot plant installed at Plataforma Solar de Almería is evaluated experimentally. The system has been tested under different ambient and operating conditions to analyze their influence on the water and electricity consumption. The results reveal that significant water savings were achieved in comparison with the conventional only-wet configuration. Concretely, a maximum water consumption saving of 67% was found at high ambient temperatures (between 25 and 30 °C) and for a thermal load of 80% when a hybrid configuration was used. The optimal operating strategies that achieve a tradeoff between low water and electricity consumption have been identified by two efficiency indexes: the specific electricity and water consumption. The parallel configuration was the optimal one in most of the cases. At high ambient temperatures and 80% thermal load, the electricity and water consumptions of this configuration were 0.033 kW_e/kW_{th} and 0.071 L/kW_{th}, respectively.

Keywords: Hybrid Cooling, Pilot Plant, Water Consumption Saving, Experimental Characterization, Optimal operating strategies

1. Introduction

Water consumption in Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants can reach values of up to 3000 m³/GW_e [1]. These plants are usually implemented in those locations with high Direct Normal Irradiance but where at the same time there is a significant water scarcity, so it is of extreme importance to reduce their water consumption. The condensation of the exhaust steam is the main source of water consumption, and it can be addressed by dry or wet cooling method.

1 Wet cooling is accomplished using two methods: once-through or evaporative wet cooling. Once-
2 through uses cold water, usually from the sea, so it allows relatively low condensation
3 temperatures, and is one of the most preferred cooling methods in terms of thermal efficiency of
4 the power cycle. However, its main drawback is the large volume of water that it uses and the
5 pollution threat to aquatic life due to the seawater extraction process and to the return of seawater
6 at a higher temperature [2]. Evaporative wet cooling is the most common method in CSP plants
7 since it relies on the wet bulb temperature and thus, leads to higher efficiency for the power block.
8 Its main problem is the requirement of a constant supply of fresh water due to the water
9 evaporation, a situation which is more aggravated in arid regions [3]. An example of the water
10 consumption is provided by a wet-cooled CSP plant located in the Mojave Desert, California,
11 which consumes about 3 m³/MWh [1]. This high amount of water makes CSP plants
12 unsustainable for such regions. Another problem of this kind of cooling systems is the generation
13 of a visible plume when the saturated exhaust air from the wet cooling tower (WCT) mixes with
14 dry and cold ambient air, especially in winter ([4–7]). It induces phenomena like fog, corrosion,
15 moisture, and darkness in the surrounding area that contribute to social concerns and, in the case
16 of CSP plants, to a possible decrease in the optical efficiency of the solar collector mirrors closest
17 to the cooling tower.

28 Dry cooling systems rely on dry bulb temperature and such plants have little or no water
29 consumption. The water consumption in a dry-cooled CSP plant can be reduced by about 95%
30 compared to wet cooling systems (having consumptions of about 0.30-0.34 m³/MWh [8]). The
31 typical examples are the Air Cooled Condensers (ACC) although there is an improved version of
32 this technology called Air Cooled Heat Exchanger (ACHE). In comparison with ACC, a power
33 plant with ACHE can produce 1% more electricity per year than the same plant with an ACC
34 system [9]. The main drawback of dry cooling systems is the higher capital costs and their
35 significant reduction in the power output (by up to 10% [1]) due to the higher condensation
36 temperature required compared to wet cooling systems and to the high electricity consumption
37 from the operation of the fans, especially at high ambient temperatures. Many efforts have been
38 made to increase the efficiency of dry cooling systems to the level of wet cooling systems [10],
39 but still there is a small percentage of these systems installed at CSP plants.

40 Several studies on the comparison between dry and wet cooling systems in CSP plants can be
41 found in the literature. Poullikas et al. [11] presented a comparative overview of evaporative
42 WCTs and ACC for the Rankine cycle of CSP plants. The comparison was performed considering
43 the overall plant's water requirements, the plant's efficiency, the plant's capital cost and the
44 plant's electricity unit cost. The authors concluded that, although ACC systems offer significant
45 reductions in water consumption against WCTs, their integration results in the overall plant's
46

1 efficiency reduction between 1-5% and increase in the overall capital costs ranging from 1% to
2 4%. This could lead to an increase in the net electricity unit cost between 2% and 9%, depending
3 on the CSP technology. Blanco-Marigorta et al. [12] also carried out a comparison between dry
4 and wet cooling technology for a CSP plant but in this case by means of an exergy analysis. They
5 found that the use of an ACC is not an efficient solution from an exergetic point of view for the
6 operation at low turbine exhaust pressures, although they are more competitive at higher
7 pressures.
8
9

10
11
12 Hybrid cooling (HC) systems are presented as a potential solution in CSP plants to cope with the
13 disadvantages of each conventional cooling method. They can reduce the water consumption by
14 up to an 80% [9] compared to wet-cooled CSP plants and enhance the performance in warm
15 weather compared to dry-cooled CSP plants [13]. Several studies on HC integrated into thermal
16 power plants can be found in the literature. Most of them are based on modelling and simulation
17 and aim for the evaluation of the performance of the thermal power plant with the HC system in
18 terms of power generation, water consumption reduction and costs. He et al. [14] developed a 1-D
19 model to predict the annual performance and water consumption of three different cooling
20 systems integrated into a geothermal power plant: a natural draft Dry Cooling Tower, a natural
21 draft WCT and a HC system. The simulations were performed taking the weather data for
22 Birdsville, Australia. From the results, it was found that water savings of 70% can be achieved
23 using the HC system in comparison with the WCT for every MW of heat rejection. In the case of
24 Zhai and Rubin [15], the authors carried out the assessment of the performance, water
25 consumption and costs for a HC system integrated into a coal or a natural-gas-fired power plant
26 with and without carbon capture and storage. The HC system was comprised of a wet-cooled
27 condenser and an ACC connected in parallel. The cost model considered the total annualized cost
28 and total levelized cost of electricity. From these results, the authors found reductions of roughly
29 91% in the water use for the HC system, but an increase of 3-5% of the Levelized Cost of
30 Electricity was observed. The paper concluded that the overall costs would be minimized if the
31 wet cooling system of the HC operated at a 30% of the total cooling load during hot periods. Hu
32 et al. [16] developed a model for a 660 MW steam power plant that integrates a HC system
33 consisting of ACC in series with a WCT. They investigated the heat transfer phenomena and the
34 water and power consumption for three operation modes: only-dry, only-wet and HC modes,
35 with respect to the change in the ambient temperature and relative humidity. It was found that at
36 high ambient temperatures and low relative humidity no benefits were observed for the HC mode
37 since the system operated as an only-wet cooling system. However, at an ambient temperature of
38 0 °C, the results were very favorable for the HC operation mode, with a 46.47% less water
39 consumption in comparison to only-wet and 45.84% less power fan consumption in comparison
40 to the only-dry operation mode. Dehaghani et al. [17] developed computational models to predict
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 the water saving of a thermal power plant located in Iran in the case that the current WCT was
2 modified by the use of a HC system (parallel wet and dry cooling system). The results were very
3 promising showing a 9.4% lower water consumption after the modifications and 64.6% less fan
4 power consumption if a high-precision air flow regulation method was used (fans with variable
5 frequency drives). Tang et al [18] evaluated the performance of a steam power plant with a HC
6 system, consisting in an ACC in parallel with a WCT, at different operating conditions (ambient
7 temperature, relative humidity, heat load). They concluded that the condensation through the
8 ACC was the best option at the following combinations of ambient temperature and thermal load:
9 16 °C/300 MW, 24 °C/225 MW and 31°C/150 MW. At higher ambient temperatures, the steam
10 condensation should be prioritized through the WCT. On the other hand, the authors of the present
11 paper [19] carried out the theoretical assessment of the best configurations of a HC system
12 integrated into a CSP plant in terms of power generation and water reduction. For this approach,
13 a model of the power block of a CSP plant (Andasol-1 type) which integrates a HC system was
14 implemented in Thermoflex software. The simulation of different configurations of the HC
15 system (composed of an ACHE and a WCT) was carried out: series, parallel, series-parallel and
16 parallel-series and for each one the water consumption and the net power generation were
17 determined. It was found that the most favorable configuration in terms of water saving was
18 series-parallel, resulting in 50% reduction of water consumption when compared to the only-wet
19 cooling option. For this configuration, a 2.5% higher power generation resulted compared to only-
20 dry cooling option. Other authors have investigated hybrid cooling towers (HCT), in which the
21 dry and wet cooling systems are integrated into the same tower. Rezaei et al. [20] developed a
22 model of a HCT able to operate in parallel or series configurations. The HCT included dry and
23 wet sections, being the dry section composed of several compact air-cooled exchangers. Finally,
24 Wei et al. [21] investigated the effect of ambient conditions over the performance of a natural
25 draft HCT and compared it with a natural draft dry cooling tower. It was found that the operation
26 of this hybrid system was more flexible than the natural draft dry cooling tower under variable
27 environmental conditions.

28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46 Regarding experimental studies, there is limited research work on HC systems tested in real
47 environment. The existing ones are based on experiments at lab-scale [22,23]. In one of these
48 studies [23], promising results were found when the HC system was selected instead of a
49 conventional wet cooling system, resulting in 35% less water consumption. These results further
50 demonstrate the need for experiments at pilot-scale in order to provide reliable data for industry.
51 In addition, the urgent need to find the best operational strategies in HC systems that reduce the
52 water requirements in CSP plants is crucial. From the theoretical work presented above, only the
53 one presented by the authors of this paper [19] has considered the integration of a HC system into
54 a CSP plant. This paper complements the previous theoretical study by an exhaustive
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 experimental analysis of a pilot scale HC system installed at the Plataforma Solar de Almería
2 (PSA), in Tabernas (Almería), Spain. This system was manufactured and then installed at PSA
3 under the framework of an EU H2020 project on Water Saving for Concentrated Solar Power
4 (WASCOP). The pilot HC system consists of an ACHE and a WCT, both sharing a surface
5 condenser that is coupled with a steam generator driven by a solar field. The steam generator
6 generates low-pressure steam (pressure between 82 and 200 mbar) with similar conditions to those
7 obtained in the exhaust steam from the power block of a CSP plant. The HC pilot plant is flexible
8 and allows the HC operation in different configurations like series, parallel, only-wet and only-
9 dry. From the results obtained from the experimental assessment¹, the optimal configurations of
10 the HC system in terms of water and electricity consumption under a wide range of operating
11 (change in the thermal load) and environmental conditions (change in the ambient temperature)
12 has been obtained.

2. Description of the test facility

23 The HC pilot plant is located at PSA, which is the largest concentrating solar technology research,
24 development and test center in Europe and is a division of the Centro de Investigaciones
25 Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT). PSA is located in Tabernas (Latitude
26 31.10 N and Longitude 2.36 W) in the South of Spain. A Typical Meteorological Year for
27 Tabernas has been obtained using Meteornom software and the resulting monthly ambient
28 temperature throughout a typical year (2005) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Average monthly data of ambient temperature at PSA-CIEMAT

52 The HC pilot plant was designed and manufactured by the French company Hammon D'Hondt.
53 The company carried out a cost-effective optimization in order to minimize the initial CAPEX
54 for the pilot plant through equipment sharing. As a result, the design that was decided was that

60 ¹ Based on experiments carried out at PSA-CIEMAT

considering a hybrid cooler composed by an ACHE and a WCT sharing the surface condenser. The design allows flexibility to test WCT and an ACHE separately (only-wet, only-dry) or in series/parallel configurations. Fig. 2 shows the simplified schematic diagram of this pilot plant that consists of three main circuits: heating, exchange and cooling.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT

2.1. The heating circuit

In the heating circuit, hot water flows inside the tube bundles of a steam generator (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 (b)) with water, coming from a condensate tank, flows inside the shell side of this steam generator. Heat is then transferred from the hot water at high pressure in the tubes to the water at low pressure in the shell and subsequently steam is generated. Hot water is provided from a storage system, which is connected to a 300 kW_{th} flat-plate solar field (see Fig. 3 (a)) by means of a heat exchanger through which the thermal energy is transferred. For the sake of brevity, no further details about the solar field are given but further information can be found in Chorak et al [24]. The water flow rate inside the tube bundles of the steam generator (FT-005) is controlled using a Proportional, Integral and Derivative (PID) controller that uses the input to the variable frequency drive of Pump 4 (SC-006 in Fig. 2) as a control signal. On the other hand, the hot water inlet temperature (TT-010) is controlled at the desired value by the aperture of Valve 3. A PID controller acts over the aperture of this valve to mix the hot water from the storage system with the colder water coming from the steam generator. By controlling hot water flow rate and inlet temperature in the steam generator, different steam flow rates can be evaluated in the pilot plant. Therefore, it allows the operation of the HC system at different thermal loads, simulating its integration into a real CSP plant that is usually under partial load conditions due to the solar radiation variability.

Fig. 3. HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT: a) flat-plate collectors of the heating circuit, b) steam generator: hot water inlet (1) and outlet (2).

2.2. The exchange circuit

In the exchange circuit, a vacuum system (Pump 5 in Fig. 2) connected to a surface condenser allows choosing the desired vacuum pressure in the circuit by a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) (in the range of 82-200 mbar). The steam generated flows into the surface condenser (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 4) where it is condensed while releasing the condensation heat to the cooling water circulating inside the tube bundle, which is in turn heated. The condensate from the surface condenser flows by gravity to a small deposit and it is then pumped to a condensate tank. The variable frequency drive of Pump 2 (SC-005 in Fig. 2) maintains the condensate level (LT-001 in Fig. 2) inside such deposit. Finally, water inside the condensate tank is pumped to the steam generator through Pump 3, closing the exchange circuit. This pump is turned on/off to maintain the level of liquid inside the steam generator (LT-002 in Fig. 2) at the desired value. Technical data for the steam generator and the surface condenser can be found in Table 1.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT, exchange circuit: (a) steam generator (1) and surface condenser (2), (b) surface condenser (1), condensate tank (2) and small deposit under the surface condenser (3).

2.3. The cooling circuit

The cooling circuit is composed of an ACHE and a WCT (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 5). Cooling water coming from both towers is pumped to the tube bundle of the surface condenser where it is heated by the heat transferred by condensation of the steam generated by the steam generator. Then, the heated cooling water flows back to the hybrid cooler to repeat the cooling process. The aperture of Valves 1 and 2 are modified to choose the desired configuration (see Table 2 and Fig. 2): only-dry, only-wet, series or parallel. In addition, a split ratio (defined as the wet fraction) can be selected in parallel configuration. The water flow rate in the tube bundle of the surface condenser (FT-003 in Fig. 2) is controlled using a PID controller that uses the variable frequency drive of Pump 1 (SC-004 Fig. 2) as control signal to maintain the nominal operating conditions despite the different head losses existing in each configuration. On the other hand, the variable frequency drives of the fans in both cooling towers (SC-001, SC-002 and SC-003 in Fig. 2) are used as control variables to maintain the inlet temperature to the surface condenser (TT-005 Fig. 2) at the desired value. Although most of the water in the cooling circuit recirculates, a small percentage of water evaporates in the WCT and must be replaced. A float valve installed in the WCT basin allows filling it with make-up water when the water level goes down. The make-up water consumed by the WCT is measured by a flow meter located at the inlet of this cooling tower (FT-004). Technical data of the cooling systems can be found in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Cooling circuit in the HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT. WCT (1) and ACHE (2)

Table 1
 Technical data of the equipment in the cooling and exchange circuits.

Steam generator

	Thermal power @42°C	80 kW _{th}
	Tube side	Hot water
	Shell side	Cold water/Steam
Surface condenser		
	Thermal power @42°C	80 kW _{th}
	Tube side	Water
	Shell side	Steam
WCT		
	Thermal power	204 kW _{th}
	Evaporation	0.28 m ³ /h
ACHE		
	Capacity	204 kW _{th}
	Exchange surface	617.58 m ²
	Power consumption	5.67 kW _e

Table 2
Configurations in the cooling circuit (see valve positions I and II in Fig. 2)

Configuration	Valve positions	
	Valve 1	Valve 2
Only-dry	II	II
Only-wet	-	I
Series	I	II
Parallel split ratio	II	Between I and II to achieve the desired split ratio

3. Methodology

3.1. Test campaign

The test campaign was designed to evaluate the different configurations of the HC system as a function of the ambient and operating conditions. Table 3 shows the range of variation for all of the variables. A total of 54 experiments were conducted in the year 2020 and 2021 and they were designed as follows (a flow chart showing the design is also depicted in Fig. 6):

- Three ambient temperature ranges were selected in order to cover the different seasons of the year in Tabernas (Almería). Note that these ranges are also typically found in other locations at the South of Europe. Here, ambient temperature between 10 and 15 °C represents the operation of the HC system in winter, ambient temperature between 18 and 23 °C represents the operation of the HC system in spring and autumn and ambient temperature between 25 and 30 °C represents the operation of the HC system in summer (see Figure 1).
- For each ambient temperature range, three thermal loads of the surface condenser were tested; a partial load of 60%, which corresponds to a thermal power between 120-125 kW_{th}; a partial load of 80%, which corresponds to a thermal power between 170- 175 kW_{th} and nominal conditions (i.e., thermal load of 100%) that corresponds to a thermal load

1 between 200-225 kW_{th}. It is important to highlight that the values selected for the thermal
2 load are not as important as the analysis of the influence of the variation of the thermal
3 load in the selection of the most suitable configuration.
4

- 5 • For each ambient temperature range and for the three thermal loads, configurations only-
6 dry (DC), only-wet (WC), series (SS) and parallel were tested. In the case of DC, WC
7 and SS, the maximum cooling flow rate (24 m³/h) circulates through both cooling towers.
8 In the case of parallel configurations, three split ratios were tested by the use of Valves 1
9 and 2 of cooling circuit (see Table 2 and Fig. 2): 25%, 50% and 75% for configurations
10 P25, P50 and P75, respectively. In the case of P25, FT-001 is 6 m³/h and FT-002 is 18
11 m³/h; in the case of P50, FT-001 and FT-002 it is 12 m³/h and in the case of P75, FT-001
12 it is 18 m³/h and for FT-002 it is 6 m³/h. The set point of cooling flow rate was established
13 in the variable frequency drive of pump 1 (SC-004 in Fig. 2).
14
- 15 • In all tests, the temperature of the steam produced by the steam generator (TT-008 in Fig.
16 2) was maintained at 45 °C. This temperature represents the condensation temperature
17 (i.e. the exhaust steam temperature) in a CSP plant. This value has been established
18 accounting that the typical condensation temperatures in CSP plants in the South of
19 Europe, where the large-scale plant market is mostly concentrated [25], are between 0.063
20 and 0.2 bar [12]. It was controlled by establishing a set point of vacuum pressure in the
21 PLC of the vacuum system (Pump 5 in Fig. 2).
22
- 23 • In all tests, the hot water flow rate flowing inside the tube bundle of the steam generator
24 (FT 005 in Fig. 2) was kept at 9.75 L/s. On the other hand, the hot water inlet temperature
25 in the steam generator (TT-010) varied between 68 °C and 76.5 °C to assure the thermal
26 loads mentioned above.
27
- 28 • Finally, the temperature at the inlet of the surface condenser (TT-005 in Fig. 2) was
29 established in all cases at 33 °C (i.e., the design temperature of this equipment). This was
30 established by the control of the variable frequency drives of both cooling towers (SC-
31 001, SC-002 and SC-003 in Fig. 2). In the case of series configuration, as the cooling
32 water is cooled firstly through the ACHE and then through the WCT, the temperatures at
33 the outlet of the ACHE (TT-003 in Fig. 2) and WCT (TT-006 in Fig. 2) were maintained
34 at 36 °C and 33 °C, respectively.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 6. Flow chart of the designed test campaign

Table 3
Range of variation of the ambient and operating variables

Variable	Range of operation
Ambient temperature, T_{amb}	(10-30) °C
Thermal load, TL	(60-100) %
Cooling water flow rate through the ACHE, FT-002	(6-24) m ³ /h
Cooling water flow rate through the WCT, FT-001	(6-24) m ³ /h
Hot water inlet temperature in the steam generator, TE-WAS-010	(68-73.5) °C
Variable frequency drives (VFD) of the ACHE, SC-002 and SC003	(11-98)%
Variable frequency drive (VFD) of the WCT, SC-001	(21-100)%

It is important to ensure steady state conditions during the operation of the HC, especially for the steam flow rate generated by the steam generator and in the case of make-up water consumed by the WCT (FT-004 in Fig. 2). In the case of the generated steam, the level of the steam generator (LT-002 in Fig. 2) was maintained at a stable level of around 330 mm to assure that the tube bundles were completely flooded. The water circulation from the surface condenser to the condensate tank was also kept as steady as possible. For that purpose, the level in the small deposit at the outlet of the surface condenser (LT-001 in Fig. 2) was maintained around 200 mm.

The data was logged every second and the average value of each variable was determined in a steady stage period of between 15-20 minutes. An error analysis was performed considering the measurement uncertainties of all the instruments. In the case of the indirect parameters an uncertainty propagation analysis was carried out to quantify the accuracy of the results. For this purpose, a tool from the Engineering Equation Solver software described in NIST Technical Note 1297 was used [26]. The measurement uncertainties of all measured variables are shown in Table 4.

Table 4
Measurement uncertainty of the direct variables

Parameter	Measurement uncertainty
Electricity consumed by the WCT, ACHE and pump	1%
1	
Make-up water consumed by the WCT	$\pm 0.5\%$ of F.S ^a + 2.5% o.r ^b
Condensate mass flow rate	$\pm 0.2\%$ o.r ^b
Saturated steam pressure	$\pm 0.3\%$ o.r ^b + 0.8% of URL ^a
Temperatures	$0.3+0.005 \cdot T^c$

^aF.S = full scale. It is 10 for FT-WAS-004 and 1.1 bar for PT-001

^bo.r = of reading

^cis the value of the temperature in °C

3.2. Assessment of the hybrid configurations

The HC configurations were evaluated by determining the improvements achieved in terms of electricity consumption reduction, in comparison to only-dry operation mode (i.e. $(ec_{DC} - ec_{HC})/ec_{DC}$) and in terms of water consumption reduction, in comparison with only-wet operation mode (i.e. $(wc_{WC} - wc_{HC})/wc_{WC}$). ec_{HC} and ec_{DC} are the electricity consumptions of the hybrid and DC configurations, respectively, and wc_{HC} and wc_{WC} are the water consumptions of the hybrid and WC configurations, respectively. The results obtained at different thermal loads and ambient temperatures are shown and explained in section 4.

The following sections describe the calculations of the electricity and water consumptions.

3.1.1. Electricity consumption

The electricity consumption (ec) is measured with an electrical energy meter (CEM-C21) installed in the electrical distribution panel of the facility that provides the instantaneous power consumption of the Pump 1 and for the WCT and ACHE fans. This consumption depends on the percentage applied to the corresponding VFD, as can be observed in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Electricity consumption measurements at different percentages applied to the VFDs.

The total measured electricity consumption is the sum of each one of the contributions (Pump 1, WCT and ACHE fans). It is important to highlight that the operating point of Pump 1 in the

1 experimental campaign described in this paper corresponds to values in the VFD, SC-004,
 2 between 91% and 97%. In the case of the ACHE operation, the values in the experimental
 3 campaign analyzed in this paper cover the whole range of SC-002 and SC-003 depicted in Fig.
 4 7, while in the case of the WCT operation, the maximum percentage required in SC-001 was
 5 40%.
 6
 7

9 3.1.2. Water consumption

10 As already mentioned, wc is measured by a flow meter located at the inlet of the make-up water
 11 pipe (FT-004 in Fig. 2). As it is evaluated when steady-state conditions are reached, the make-up
 12 flow can be considered to correspond to the water evaporated in the WCT.
 13
 14
 15
 16

17 3.3. Efficiency calculation and selection of optimal configurations

18 Two efficiency indexes that determine the specific electricity energy consumption (SEC) and the
 19 specific water consumption (SWC) are proposed to decide which is the optimal configuration
 20 according to the ambient and operating conditions. There must be a trade-off between the water
 21 and the electricity consumption, considering also the relation of these values with the thermal
 22 power. In other words, optimal configurations will be the ones that allow reducing as much as
 23 possible the water and electricity consumptions per kW_{th} used to condense the available steam.
 24 These indexes are thus a measurement of the efficiency of the system since they relate the
 25 consumptions that penalize the process with the rejected heat, which would be in turn related with
 26 the electricity produced in a real turbine. The calculation of these indexes is as follows:
 27
 28
 29
 30
 31
 32
 33
 34
 35

$$36 SEC \left(\frac{kW_e}{kW_{th}} \right) = \frac{ec}{TP}, \quad (1)$$

$$37 SWC \left(\frac{L/h}{kW_{th}} \right) = \frac{wc}{TP}, \quad (2)$$

38 where ec is the electricity consumption measured in kW_e , wc is the water consumption in L/h and
 39 TP is the thermal power of the surface condenser measured in kW_{th} . It is defined as the heat
 40 transfer rate by condensation of the steam generated and can be determined by Eq.**Error!**
 41
 42
 43
 44
 45
 46
 47

48 **Reference source not found.:**

$$49 TP = \dot{m}_s \lambda_{cond} + \dot{m}_c (h_{l,sat} - h_c), \quad (3)$$

50 where \dot{m}_s is the steam mass flow rate generated by the steam generator, λ_{cond} is the latent heat
 51 of condensation at the pressure measured in PT-001 (see Fig. 2), \dot{m}_c is the condensate mass flow
 52 rate at the outlet of the surface condenser, $h_{l,sat}$ is the specific enthalpy of saturated liquid in the
 53
 54
 55
 56
 57
 58
 59
 60
 61
 62
 63
 64
 65

surface condenser at pressure PT-001 and h_c is the specific enthalpy of the subcooled condensate leaving the surface condenser, at the temperature TT-007 (see Fig. 2) and pressure PT-001.

Notice that, as the evaluation of the HC is performed at steady state conditions, the steam entering the surface condenser is completely condensed, so it can be assumed that $\dot{m}_s = \dot{m}_c$. In addition, the VFD of Pump 2 is regulated to maintain LT-001 at a steady-state value, so the mass flow rate at the outlet of the surface condenser (\dot{m}_c) is that measured in FT-006 (see Fig. 2).

The optimal configurations are obtained by a cost function, J_{ijk} , which is evaluated for each configuration, i , thermal load, j , and ambient temperature, k , being $i=\{WC,P75,P50,P25,SS,DC\}$, $j=\{TL-60,TL-80,TL-100\}$ and $k=\{(10-15), (18-23), (25-30)\}$ °C:

$$J_{ijk} = \alpha_1 \cdot \frac{SEC_{ijk} - SEC_{jk}^{min}}{SEC_{jk}^{max} - SEC_{jk}^{min}} + \alpha_2 \cdot \frac{SWC_{ijk} - SWC_{jk}^{min}}{SWC_{jk}^{max} - SWC_{jk}^{min}}, \quad (4)$$

$$SEC_{jk}^{min} = \min\{SEC_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}, \quad (5)$$

$$SEC_{jk}^{max} = \max\{SEC_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}, \quad (6)$$

where SEC and SWC are normalized to bring all values into the range [0,1] and α_1 and α_2 are weighting factors to tune the importance of each term in relation to the other. In this case, the values established for these factors are: $\alpha_1=1$ and $\alpha_2=1.2$, because the priority is to reduce the water consumption. The optimal value for each load and ambient temperature range, θ_{jk} , corresponds to that configuration that gives the minimum value of J :

$$\theta_{jk} = \min_i \{J_{ijk}\} \quad \forall i = \{WC, P75, P50, P25, SS, DC\}. \quad (7)$$

4. Results

4.1 Variation of the electricity consumption

This section shows the variation of the electricity consumption and of the temperatures in the cooling circuit (i.e., the inlet and outlet temperatures from the ACHE and WCT) with the TL and with the ambient temperature for the different HC configurations (see Fig. 8 and Fig. 9). TL-100 corresponds to the operation at thermal load 100%, TL-80 to the operation at thermal load 80% and TL-60 to the operation at thermal load 60%. In addition, this section shows the percentages of ec reduction of the HC configurations in comparison to configuration only-dry (the one with the highest electricity consumption) for the different TL and ambient temperature ranges (see Table 5). The errors obtained from the uncertainty propagation analysis are also shown in this table together with the percentage results.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 8. Effect of the thermal load on the electricity consumption for a) T_{amb} (10-15) °C; b) (18-23) °C and c) (25-30) °C. All the errors are represented as error bars

Fig. 9. Temperatures in the cooling circuit at different ambient temperature ranges (H: (25-30) °C, M: (18-23) °C, L: (13-15) °C) at a TL (a) 100%, (b) 80% and (c) 60%. The maximum error of the temperature measurements is 0.5 °C (see Table 1).

As observed in Fig. 8, the value of ec increased in all configurations with the thermal load and with the ambient temperature. The increase with the thermal load is explained by the rise in the cooling water temperatures at the inlet of the WCT and ACHE (TT-001 and TT-002, respectively)

1 when the TP in the surface condenser increases, as can be seen in Fig. 9. Such a temperature rise
2 leads to a higher percentage required in SC-001, SC-002 and SC-003 to achieve the desired
3 temperature at the inlet of the surface condenser (33 °C). Likewise, higher percentages in SC-001,
4 SC-002 and SC-003 are directly related to a higher electricity consumption of the cooling system,
5 as indicated in Fig. 7. On the other hand, the higher the ambient temperature the higher the
6 percentage needed in the VFD of both cooling towers to achieve the cooling requirements, which
7 leads to a rise in the ec , as seen in Fig. 7. This ec increase is especially significant in the case of
8 the ACHE (configuration DC), as seen in Fig. 8, since in this case the ec increases at a higher rate
9 the higher the percentage used in SC-002 and SC-003 is. For the rest of configurations, it can be
10 seen that at low and medium ambient temperatures, there are no significant differences between
11 them in terms of ec , for the different thermal loads. It can be seen that WC, SS, P75 and P25 have
12 similar ec , and the configuration P50 was the one with the lowest electricity consumptions. It is
13 important to highlight that, although a lower ec for configuration WC is expected compared with
14 the HC configurations, the head losses in the cooling circuit for this configuration are higher than
15 for the others, which led to a higher electricity consumed by Pump 1. At high ambient
16 temperatures, the differences in ec between configurations became more significant, especially at
17 higher thermal loads. At TL-80, the configurations that showed the highest ec were P25 and SS
18 and at TL-100, P50 and SS.

19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31 The results shown in Table 5 can help select the most suitable configurations in terms of ec
32 reduction compared to the conventional only-dry cooling system. As it can be seen, the ec
33 reduction of configurations P50, P75, P25, WC and SS with respect the configuration for only-
34 dry was higher the higher the thermal load and ambient temperature were. This is a reasonable
35 result given the reasons mentioned before regarding the significant effect of both variables (TL
36 and ambient temperature) in the ec of the ACHE. At low ambient temperatures (i.e., between 10
37 and 15 °C) and the lowest TL (TL-60), the percentage of reduction in the ec with respect to the
38 operation with configuration only-dry was not very significant, and the highest value was 11.7%
39 for configuration P25. When the TL was increased up to 80%, the percentage of ec reduction
40 compared to only-dry became more significant for some configurations, thus P50 showed the
41 higher ec reduction (24.0%), followed by P25 that achieved a percentage of ec reduction of
42 18.9%. At nominal conditions (TL-100), the HC operation allowed an important ec reduction
43 compared to the conventional only-dry operation and the same configurations as before (P50 or
44 P25) achieved higher improvements in terms of ec (the percentages of reduction were 34.7% and
45 28.6%, respectively). At medium ambient temperatures (i.e., between 18 and 23 °C), the
46 percentages of ec reduction increased with respect to the operation at low ambient temperatures,
47 being more pronounced at higher TL s. In the case of TL-60, the recommended configuration in
48 terms of ec saving would be P50, since it showed the highest ec reduction (34.0%). At TL-80,
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

apart from P50 (whose percentage of *ec* reduction compared with DC was 46.7%), P75 also gave good results (40.0% of *ec* reduction), so these two HC configurations could be suitable in case *ec* is prioritized. At nominal load, the same HC configurations are recommended in terms of *ec* reduction. Finally, at high ambient temperatures (i.e. between 25 and 30 °C), the percentages of *ec* reduction in comparison with the only-dry configuration were the highest ones, achieving values close to 50%. Among the tests performed at the lowest *TL*, it was found that the operation with configurations P50, P75 and WC is recommended when a significant *ec* reduction is required compared with the conventional only-dry configuration. The percentages of reduction obtained were 44.4% for P50, 40.1% for P75 and 40.6% for WC.

Table 5
Percentages of electricity consumption reduction of the HC configurations with the associated errors in comparison to configuration only-dry for the different thermal loads and ambient temperature ranges

Configuration	Thermal Load	Ambient temperature ranges		
		(10-15) °C	(18-23) °C	(25-30) °C
WC	TL-60	(4.6±1.3)%	(22.4±1.1)%	(40.6±0.8)%
	TL-80	(11.2±1.3)%	(38.8±0.9)%	(52.7±0.7)%
	TL-100	(23.7±1.1)%	(53.8±0.7)%	(49.7±0.7)%
P75	TL-60	(8.1±1.2)%	(24.7±1.1)%	(40.1±0.8)%
	TL-80	(14.5±1.2)%	(40.0±0.8)%	(52.7±0.7)%
	TL-100	(25.8±1.1)%	(54.6±0.6)%	(49.7±0.7)%
P50	TL-60	(22.7±1.2)%	(34.0±0.9)%	(44.4±0.8)%
	TL-80	(24.0±1.1)%	(46.7±0.7)%	(46.4±0.8)%
	TL-100	(34.7±0.9)%	(59.4±0.6)%	(0.0±1.4)%
P25	TL-60	(15.4±1.2)%	(28.7±1.0)%	(28.8±1.0)%
	TL-80	(18.9±1.1)%	(38.6±0.9)%	(3.1±1.4)%
	TL-100	(28.6±0.9)%	(53.2±0.7)%	(1.4±1.4)%
SS	TL-60	(4.4±1.3)%	(22.2±1.1)%	(37.9±0.9)%
	TL-80	(10.7±1.3)%	(37.6±0.9)%	(25.2±1.1)%
	TL-100	(23.1±1.1)%	(50.6±0.7)%	(22.4±1.1)%

4.2 Variation of the water consumption

This section shows the variation of the water consumption of the HC at different TL and ambient temperature (see Fig. 10). In addition, it shows the percentages of wc reduction of the HC configurations in comparison to configuration only-wet, which can be found in Table 6.

Fig. 10. Effect of the thermal load on the water consumption for a) T_{amb} (10-15) °C; b) (18-23) °C and c) (25-30) °C. All the errors are represented as error bars

As observed in Fig. 10, w_c increased in all configurations with the thermal load, except in the case of configuration SS. This increase is due to the rise in the cooling water temperature at the inlet of the WCT with the thermal load (see Fig. 9). An increase in this cooling water temperature leads to a higher energy demand required to reduce the enthalpy of the water through the WCT to reach the desired 33 °C at the outlet. Then, the air flow rate must increase (by means of the VFD of the fan) in order to cover such energy demand, causing higher losses by evaporation and consequently higher water consumptions. In series configuration, w_c presented similar values at different TLs because the cooling water temperature at the inlet of the WCT (TT-001 in Fig. 9) was maintained at 36 °C. This makes the VFD of the fan work at similar operating conditions, as the air flow rate were then similar and therefore the losses by evaporation also.

Regarding the behaviour of the w_c with respect to the ambient temperature, it is expected that the water consumption in the WCT increases with increasing ambient temperature because the energy demand required to reduce the enthalpy of the water through the tower (and reach 33 °C at the outlet) depends on the air enthalpy difference between the outlet and the inlet. Since the air inlet enthalpy increases with the ambient temperature, the air flow rate must increase (by means of the VFD of the fan) in order to cover the energy demand, causing higher losses by evaporation (i.e., higher water consumptions). As seen in Fig. 10, this increase was observed in the case of configurations WC and P75. However, in the case of P50 and P25 configurations, the tendency was opposite to the previous cases and the w_c decreased with the ambient temperature. This fact is directly related to the cooling capacity of the WCT. When the WCT is operating with medium-low cooling flow rates (12 m³/h in the case of P50 and 6 m³/h in the case of P25) and the ambient

temperature and/or the water inlet enthalpy are low (i.e. partial loads), the temperature at the outlet of the WCT (TT-006 in Fig. 9) is under 33 °C because the minimum fan percentage (21%) is achieved. Therefore, the air mass flow in these cases is higher than needed in order to achieve the required operating conditions and the losses by evaporation are higher than expected. To understand this fact better, configuration P50 at TL-100 is taken as an example. At low ambient temperature, the VFD of the WCT was at the minimum value, and the outlet temperature of the WCT was lower than required, 30 °C. Then, it can be seen in Fig. 9 that the temperature difference between the inlet (TT-001) and the outlet of the WCT (TT-006) was higher at low ambient temperatures than at high ambient temperatures, which is directly related to the water consumption as explained previously.

In the case of SS configuration, as already mentioned, the water inlet temperature to the WCT is always maintained at 36 °C (TT-001 in Fig. 9), and a similar water consumption can be observed for the three ambient temperature ranges. This is caused because the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet temperatures in the WCT was low (only 3 °C), which led to a low required heat transfer to achieve this temperature difference through water evaporation.

The comparison between configurations was carried out by evaluating the water consumption reduction in the case of using a HC configuration instead of an only-wet configuration, which is the configuration with the highest wc. The values obtained together with the resulting errors from the uncertainty propagation analysis can be found in Table 6.

Table 6
Percentages of water consumption reduction of the HC configurations with the associated errors in comparison to configuration only-wet for the different thermal loads and ambient temperature ranges.

Configuration	Thermal Load	Ambient temperature ranges		
		(10-15) °C	(18-23) °C	(25-30) °C
P75	TL-60	(26.2±9.9)%	(23.2±10.0)%	(24.2±9.1)%
	TL-80	(26.9±7.9)%	(23.0±8.02)%	(38.1±6.5)%
	TL-100	(27.9±7.1)%	(21.8±7.2)%	(23.6±6.7)%
P50	TL-60	(33.9±9.4)%	(22.8±10.0)%	(38.7±8.1)%
	TL-80	(33.6±7.4)%	(38.6±7.1)%	(51.6±5.8)%
	TL-100	(33.0±6.8)%	(41.6±6.1)%	(43.3±5.6)%
P25	TL-60	(50.2±8.3)%	(47.8±8.3)%	(56.9±7.0)%
	TL-80	(60.4±5.9)%	(59.7±5.9)%	(66.9±5.0)%
	TL-100	(58.2±5.4)%	(61.6±5.0)%	(61.3±4.7)%
	TL-60	(27.2±9.9)%	(25.6±9.8)%	(37.3±8.2)%

SS	TL-80	(44.3±6.8)%	(44.7±6.7)%	(52.8±5.7)%
	TL-100	(54.4±5.6)%	(57.9±5.2)%	(59.7±4.8)%

As expected, the highest *wc* reduction was obtained from configuration P25 (66.9% at high ambient temperature and TL-80) since this is the configuration with the least use of the WCT, with only 6 m³/h of water flow rate through the WCT. On the opposite side, P75 was the HC configuration that makes the highest use of the WCT (18 m³/h of water flow rate) so it achieved the lowest water reduction in comparison to configuration only-wet (24.2% at medium ambient temperature and TL-60).

The water consumption reduction in configuration P25 increased with *TL* and ambient temperature between 50.2% and 66.9%, a considerable reduction that emphasizes the importance of combining wet and dry cooling to reduce the water consumption throughout the year and for all thermal loads. In the case of SS configuration, the percentages of water consumption reduction also increased with the ambient temperature and *TL* but it was more significant at TL-80 and TL-100 (between 44.7% and 59.7%). At low thermal load, TL-60, the percentage of increase was between 25.6% and 37.2%, which was closer to the values obtained with parallel configurations. The percentages of increase with configuration P50 were lower than in the previous cases and did not show a specific tendency with the ambient temperature and the *TL* because of the WCT cooling capacity limitation in some of the experiments, as explained previously. In the case of configuration P75, the percentages at different *TL*s and several ambient temperatures varied over a narrow range (between 21.8% and 27.9%), and did not follow a clear tendency because the water consumption in this configuration was closer to the one obtained with configuration only-wet.

4.2. Optimal configurations

Fig. 11 shows the results of *SEC* and *SWC* obtained for each one of the configurations, thermal loads and ambient temperature ranges. The maximum error obtained from the uncertainty analysis resulted of 0.0007 kW_e/kW_{th} and 0.11 L/h·kW_{th} for the *SEC* and *SWC*, respectively. The optimal configurations obtained are represented in bold type.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Fig. 11. *SWC* against *SEC* for each configuration, at different thermal loads and at different ambient temperature ranges (a) (10-15) °C, (b) (18-23) °C and (c) (25-30) °C. Optimal configurations are represented in bold type.

At low ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (a)), the best results were obtained from configuration P25 at TL-60 and TL-80. At this ambient temperature, the electricity consumption in the ACHE is low, so it is recommended to operate as much as possible with this configuration in order to reduce the water consumption. At TL-100, configuration P50 gave better results than P25, due to the difference of the electricity consumption between these two configurations. Configuration P25 resulted also the best one in the case of medium ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (b)), but it is also important to highlight that configuration P50 allowed to reduce the *SEC* even more at the expense of increasing the *SWC*. It is important to mention that for all ambient temperature ranges, the lowest specific consumptions were obtained operating at TL-100, which means that partial loads penalize the consumption per kW_{th}. In the case of high ambient temperatures (Fig. 11 (c)), the specific consumptions increased, mainly because of the electricity consumption in the ACHE. For this reason, at high ambient temperatures it would be recommended to reduce the use of the ACHE, being the optimal configurations SS at TL-100 and P50 at TL-80 and TL-60.

5. Conclusions

This study deals with the assessment of the best operating strategies of a HC system in terms of reduction in the water and electricity consumptions in comparison with the conventional only-dry and only-wet cooling systems. An exhaustive experimental campaign has been carried out at a HC pilot plant at PSA-CIEMAT, testing different configurations over a wide range of operating (different thermal loads) and ambient (different ambient temperatures) conditions. The results obtained from this study can help the CSP industry to invest in HC solutions at industrial scale, since it has been proven that there are strategies that allow to reach a trade-off between the water and the electricity consumption depending on the thermal load of the power block and on the ambient temperature. The main conclusions obtained from the experimental evaluation are given below:

- The most favorable configuration in terms of reduction in the electricity consumption at all tested conditions is a parallel one with a split ratio of 50%. For this configuration, a maximum reduction of 59.3% was obtained compared to the only-dry configuration, at nominal load (TL-100) and high ambient temperature (18-23 °C).
- Configuration parallel with a split ratio of 25% has shown the highest reduction in the water consumption when compared with a conventional only-wet configuration. A percentage of 66.9% was obtained when the pilot plant operated at a thermal load of 80% and the ambient temperature was between 25 and 30 °C.
- The assessment of the optimal operating strategies has been achieved by the evaluation of two efficiency indicators, which consider the relation of the water and electricity consumptions with the thermal power required to condensate the available steam. These efficiency indicators are the *SEC* and the *SWC*.
- At low ambient temperatures, the optimal strategy at partial loads (TL-80 and TL-100) is the operation with configuration parallel with split ratio of 25%. However, when the load is reduced to TL-60, it is recommended to change the strategy, and operate with configuration parallel with split ratio of 50%.
- At medium ambient temperatures, the best strategy is to operate with configuration parallel with a split ratio of 25% at all thermal loads.
- In the case of high ambient temperatures, the most favorable strategy at partial loads (TL-60 and TL-80) is the operation with configuration parallel with a split ratio of 50%. When the thermal load increases at TL-100, the strategy should be changed to

configuration series that provide an optimal trade-off between the water and electricity consumption.

Nomenclature

Symbols

TP	Thermal power, kW _{th}
Ec	Electricity consumption in the cooling circuit, kW _e
ec_{DC}	Electricity consumption in only-dry configuration, kW _e
ec_{HC}	Electricity consumption in a hybrid configuration, kW _e
ec_{WC}	Electricity consumption in only-wet configuration, kW _e
h_c	Specific enthalpy of the condensate, kJ/kg
$h_{l,sat}$	Specific enthalpy of the saturated liquid, kJ/kg
\dot{m}_c	Condensate mass flow rate (FT-006 in Fig. 2), kg/s
\dot{m}_s	Steam mass flow rate between the steam generator and the surface condenser, kg/s
SEC	Specific electric energy consumption, kW _e /kW _{th}
SWC	Specific water consumption, L/h·kW _{th}
T_{amb}	Ambient temperature, °C
TL	Thermal load, %
wc	Water consumption, L/h
wc_{HC}	Water consumption in a hybrid configuration, L/h
wc_{WC}	Water consumption in only-wet configuration, L/h

1 λ_{cond} Latent heat of condensation, kJ/kg

2
3
4 *Abbreviations*

5
6
7 ACC Air Cooled Condensers

8
9
10 ACHE Air Cooler Heat Exchanger

11
12
13 CIEMAT Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y
14 Tecnológicas

15
16
17 CSP Concentrated Solar Power

18
19
20 DC Only-dry

21
22
23 VFD Variable Frequency Drive

24
25
26 HC Hybrid cooling

27
28
29 HCT Hybrid cooling tower

30
31
32 PID Proportional, Integral and Derivative control

33
34
35 PLC Programmable Logic Controller

36
37
38 PSA Plataforma Solar de Almería

39
40
41 P25 Parallel with a split ratio of 25%

42
43
44 P50 Parallel with a split ratio of 50%

45
46
47 P75 Parallel with a split ratio of 75%

48
49
50 SS Series

51
52
53 WASCOP Water Saving for Concentrated Solar Power

54
55
56 WC Only-wet

57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Acknowledgments

We thank the Plataforma Solar de Almeria for providing access to its installations

References

- [1] K. Damerau, K. Williges, A.G. Patt, P. Gauché, Costs of reducing water use of concentrating solar power to sustainable levels : Scenarios for North Africa, *Energy Policy*. 39 (2011) 4391–4398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2011.04.059>.
- [2] S.W. Mohammed Ali, N. Vahedi, C. Romero, A. Oztekin, An optimization for water requirement in natural gas combined cycle power plants equipped with once-through and hybrid cooling systems and carbon capture unit, *Water-Energy Nexus*. 3 (2020) 117–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wen.2020.08.001>.
- [3] M. Martín, M. Martín, Cooling limitations in power plants : Optimal multiperiod design of natural draft cooling towers, *Energy*. 135 (2017) 625–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.06.171>.
- [4] A. Corti, E. Carnevale, Environmental impact from wet plumes in combined-cycle power plants, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 18 (1998) 1049–1057. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-4311\(98\)00029-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-4311(98)00029-5).
- [5] S.K. Tyagi, A.K. Pandey, P.C. Pant, V. V. Tyagi, Formation, potential and abatement of plume from wet cooling towers: A review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 16 (2012) 3409–3429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.059>.
- [6] T.M.L. Wigley, P.R. Slawson, The effect of atmospheric conditions on the length of visible cooling tower plumes, *Atmos. Environ.* 9 (1975) 437–445.
- [7] X. Xu, S. Wang, Z. Ma, Evaluation of plume potential and plume abatement of evaporative cooling towers in a subtropical region, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 28 (2008) 1471–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2007.09.003>.
- [8] C. Turchi, K. Chuck, Water use in concentrating solar power (CSP), (2009). <http://www.swhydro.arizona.edu/renewable/presentations/thursday/turchi.pdf>.
- [9] A. Colmenar-Santos, D. Borge-Diez, C.P. Molina, M. Castro-Gil, Water consumption in solar parabolic trough plants : review and analysis of the southern Spain case, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 34 (2014) 565–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.03.042>.
- [10] K. Hooman, Z. Guan, H. Gurgenci, Advances in dry cooling for concentrating solar thermal (CST) power plants, Elsevier Ltd, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100516-3.00009-5>.
- [11] A. Poullikkas, I. Hadjipaschalis, G. Kourtis, A comparative overview of wet and dry cooling systems for Rankine cycle based CSP plants, *Trends Heat Mass Transf.* 13 (2013) 27–50.
- [12] A.M. Blanco-Marigorta, M. Victoria Sanchez-Henríquez, J.A. Peña-Quintana, Exergetic comparison of two different cooling technologies for the power cycle of a thermal power plant, *Energy*. 36 (2011) 1966–1972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2010.09.033>.
- [13] C. Kutscher, D. Costenaro, Assessment of evaporative cooling enhancement methods for air-cooled geothermal power plants, No. NREL/CP-550-32394. Natl. Renew. Energy Lab., Golden, CO.(US). (2002) 1–9. <http://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy02osti/32394.pdf>.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [14] S. He, H. Gurgenci, Z. Guan, K. Hooman, Z. Zou, Comparative study on the performance of natural draft dry, pre-cooled and wet cooling towers, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 99 (2016) 103–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2016.01.060>.
 - [15] H. Zhai, E.S. Rubin, A techno-economic assessment of hybrid cooling systems for coal- and natural-gas-fired power plants with and without carbon capture and storage, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50 (2016) 4127–4134. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b00008>.
 - [16] H. Hu, Z. Li, Y. Jiang, X. Du, Thermodynamic characteristics of thermal power plant with hybrid (dry/wet) cooling system, *Energy*. 147 (2018) 729–741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.01.074>.
 - [17] S. Taghian Dehaghani, H. Ahmadikia, Retrofit of a wet cooling tower in order to reduce water and fan power consumption using a wet/dry approach, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 125 (2017) 1002–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.07.069>.
 - [18] T. Tang, J. Xu, S. Jin, H. Wei, Study on Operating Characteristics of Power Plant with Dry and Wet Cooling Systems, *Energy Power Eng.* 05 (2013) 651–656. <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2013.54b126>.
 - [19] F. Asfand, P. Palenzuela, L. Roca, A. Caron, C.-A. Lemarié, J. Gillard, P. Turner, K. Patchigolla, Thermodynamic performance and water consumption of hybrid cooling system configurations for concentrated solar power plants, *Sustainability*. 12 (2020) 1–19.
 - [20] E. Rezaei, S. Shafiei, A. Abdollahnezhad, Reducing water consumption of an industrial plant cooling unit using hybrid cooling tower, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 51 (2010) 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2009.09.027>.
 - [21] H. Wei, X. Huang, L. Chen, L. Yang, X. Du, Performance of a novel natural draft hybrid cooling tower for thermal power generation, *Energy Procedia*. 158 (2019) 5231–5237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.01.661>.
 - [22] W. Asvapoositkul, M. Kuansathan, Comparative evaluation of hybrid (dry/wet) cooling tower performance, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 71 (2014) 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.06.023>.
 - [23] M. Deziani, K. Rahmani, S.J. Mirrezaei Roudaki, M. Kordloo, Feasibility study for reduce water evaporative loss in a power plant cooling tower by using air to air heat exchanger with auxiliary fan, *Desalination*. 406 (2017) 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2015.12.007>.
 - [24] A. Chorak, P. Palenzuela, D.C. Alarcón-Padilla, A. Ben Abdellah, Experimental characterization of a multi-effect distillation system coupled to a flat plate solar collector field: Empirical correlations, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 120 (2017) 298–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.03.115>.
 - [25] W. Weiss, M. Spörk-Dür, Solar heat worldwide: Global market development and trends in 2020, 2021.
 - [26] B.N. Taylor, C.E. Kuyatt, Guidelines for evaluating and expressing the uncertainty of NIST measurement results, 1994. <http://physics.nist.gov/TN1297>.

Figure 5

(a) T_{amb} (10-15) °C

(b) T_{amb} (18-23) °C

(c) T_{amb} (25-30) °C

